

Deliverable 4.3

A strategic five-year R I plan in the three thematic areas

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1 Summary

UNITA's Work Package 4 (WP4) on Research and Innovation (R&I) focuses on the three core thematic areas of the alliance: Cultural Heritage (CH), Circular Economy (CE), and Renewable Energies (RE). Its first task led by UPPA is devoted to “*focussing research on territories*” (Task 4.1). In order to fulfil the activities planned in the Grant Agreement and corresponding to “*connect research and learning*” (Task 4.2) and to “*energize the territories*” (Task 4.3), three R&I Hubs have been created and designed. The elaboration of these hubs has been a first challenge, and it has been achieved in the frame of two sub tasks (Task 4.1.1, with deliverable D 4.1.1 “*Identifying actors in the three main areas*” and task 4.1.2 with associated deliverable 4.1.2 “*Designing models for UNITA R&I Hubs*”). After only one year of operation for these hubs, the results that have been obtained are numerous, and we are able to draw “*A strategic five-year R&I plan in the three thematic areas*”, in the form of an ambition for their development and extension. In this deliverable, we will hence focus on the results that were obtained (also from associated Horizon Europe SwafS Initiative project n° 101035810 Re-

UNITA, devoted to research), and describe the “ambition” for the potential future of the hubs that would make them Reference Institutes at a European level, for research and innovation devoted to the development of our territories and stakeholders in the three (or more) thematic areas.

2 Introduction and background

2.1 Need for hubs

UNITA's Work Package 4 (WP4) on Research and Innovation (R&I) focuses on three main thematic areas (Cultural Heritage, Circular Economy, and Renewable Energies) in order to contribute to the development of rural and mountain areas through promoting the value of the natural resources, developing circular economy networks (including bio-economy), linking different economic activities (agriculture, tourism, industry and crafts), promoting the richness of the cultural and linguistic heritage, and optimizing the relationships between the different actors of each ecosystem.

Each of these thematic areas responds to a particular crisis, or societal challenge, that we all face today in Europe. Cultural heritage is pivotal today as it reinforces Europe's cultural identity in the face of Brexit, populist or extremist ideologies, or even the current COVID-19 crisis. Circular economy is a vital issue to examine in order to empower responsible consumers, invent more sustainable products, and reduce waste at all levels of the production and consumption chain. Renewable Energies are critical in order to place the European Union at the forefront of the fight against environmental pollution and global warming and to make energy accessible to all. Nevertheless, facing societal challenges and sustainable development goals may require interdisciplinary actions across the identified thematic areas and others at their interface.

UNITA wishes to raise awareness about these societal challenges in order to strengthen our rural territories, empower our cross-border mountain communities, and reduce inequalities between the core (cities where the universities are located) and its peripheries (territories) through a creative combination of education and research. The is committed to delivering world-class quality research through innovative collaborations and pioneering projects on topics crucial to today's European Union. UNITA will create a synergy amongst students and researchers of our six universities and local stakeholders and companies of the regions concerned. In order to achieve this synergy across Southern Europe, UNITA launched three Research & Innovation Hubs around Cultural Heritage, Circular Economy and Renewable Energies. These hubs constitute networks of researchers across universities working on

projects in close collaboration with students and local stakeholders in the public and the private sectors.

2.2 Preliminary steps to hubs design

2.2.1 Connecting researchers

In order to build these hubs, it has been first necessary to “*Identify actors in the three main areas*” (Sub task 4.1.1). Indeed, as stated in Deliverable 4.1.1 by the end of May 2021 the first version of a cartography of the research activities being carried out in the alliance was set up. It was the outcome of a call for expression of interest that was proposed to all the researchers of the alliance but also from work that was performed by groups of researchers that collected, analysed and organized the answers to this call. These groups were the embryos of the hubs whose daily operation are described in the present document. This cartography was also the first step towards making every researcher from UNITA aware of possible collaborations within the alliance.

2.2.2 Organizing hub governance

For a daily and efficient operation of the hubs, it was necessary to design a “model for governance”. As explained in deliverable 4.1.2 “*Designing models for UNITA R&I Hubs*”, released on the 30th of November 2021, operation of the R&I hubs could not be described without explaining its links with the overall project. Indeed, R&I Hubs activities take place in the frame of the WP4, which itself, is a part of the European University UNITA and its different boards. Most of the progress of the project is being considered by UNITA Management Committee before being escalated to the Governance Board, and WP4 acts as a connection between research activities carried out in the hubs and these managerial and decisional boards. On the other hand, UNITA offices are key actors in the daily operation of all UNITA activities, including, among others, a support for research activities. This means that they also need to have a specific position and connection with the R&I Hubs. Taking into consideration these different elements, the final organization of the WP4 was proposed. As shown on Figure 1, it is composed of a Coordinating Committee, the three R&I Hubs and the UNITA offices. More information regarding the exact role and composition of the Coordinating committee and hubs might be found elsewhere (D 4.1.2 “*Designing models for UNITA R&I Hubs*”)

Figure 1 : Organisation of the WP4 and its coordinating committee.

2.2.3 UNITA Associated partners

As a premise of the proposal to extend UNITA to UNITA 2.0 (2022 Erasmus+ European Universities call) four universities were declared as “UNITA Associated Partners” at the Governance Board held at UBI in Covilha on the 26 of November 2021. These UAPs are:

- *Instituto Politécnico da Guarda* (IPG) in Portugal,
- *Universidad Pública de Navarra* (UPNA) in Spain,
- *Università degli Studi di Brescia* (UNIBS) in Italy and
- *Universitatea Transilvania Braşov* (UniTBv) in Romania

It was also decided at that time that these UAPs should contribute to WP4 activities. This leads to an increase in the task forces of the hubs as well as an extension of the “[WP4 cartography](#)” aiming at identifying and mapping all ongoing projects and research activities related to UNITA’s core thematic.

2.3 Re-UNITA

Re-UNITA (Research for UNITA) project (N° 101035810) is funded under the call “H2020-IBASwafS-support-2-2020”, for a duration of 36 months, and started on the 01/09/2021, within UNITA. Re-UNITA activities focus on the goal of the Alliance to become a major player in the construction of the new European Research Area, by developing a common strategy for Research and Innovation.

The project implements the first steps in order to develop a common research and innovation agenda. Further actions also focus on intellectual property and attractiveness among the Alliance territories, sharing infrastructures, reinforcing the cooperation with non-academic stake holders (including citizens and civil society), knowledge transfer, and developing open science practices.

Re-UNITA Work Package 1 is devoted to the management of the project, and indeed, is composed by the 6 Vice Reactors for Research of the Alliance (Mrs Silvia Socorro for UBI, Mrs

Isabelle Baraille for UPPA, Mrs Mareva Sabatier for USMB, Mr Florin Sava for UVT, Mrs Cristina Prandi for UNITO and Mrs Rosa Bolea for UNIZAR). With its monthly meetings, this offers a particularly relevant place to discuss Common Research Policy and more particularly and the work of the Three thematic hubs. This gives a political complement to the WP4 coordinating committee for strategic decisions to be taken.

Figure 2: General organisation chart of UNITA and Re-UNTA

Both Management committees are the place where actions of the WP's are being discussed and organised, with particular importance of their WP1 (board of Vice Rectors for Internationalisation in UNITA and board for Vice Rectors for Research for Re-UNITA)

3 Activity report after one year of operation

3.1 Task Forces

Hubs would be nothing without their task forces that have a strong involvement and commitment. At the time this report is prepared, they are composed of 22, 31, and 18 researchers for Cultural Heritage, Renewable Energy and Circular Economy hubs, respectively. These task forces have monthly meetings where activities to be prepared for the project (Micro Credentials, Summer/winter schools, online seminars...) are discussed and distributed over the partners to reach the objective of the overall project.

Even though the objective of having 30 researchers enrolled in the hubs (Indicator 4.1 *Numbers of researchers involved in the R&I Hubs*) is reached, it is still necessary to integrate stakeholders to complete the task forces. Such an enrolment has been difficult to fulfil up to now, since most of the activities of the hubs have been devoted to internal organisation and delivery of the expected tasks of the projects (WP4 deliverables). Anyway, one can bank on

the fact that with the help of UNITA’s advisory council, and of the results of Re-UNITA deliverable 6.1 “Database of the local and regional civil society’s actors from UNITA’s surrounding ecosystem.” that will be submitted to ERA in November 2022, involvement of stakeholders within the hubs task forces will be made easier. This is all the more true in that for the final year of the project, hubs are expected to answer European calls for projects aiming at answering societal challenges of the mountain and rural territories of UNITA, in association with stakeholders. Answering these calls will require some extra work and energy to bring together the researchers of the alliance who have the desired skills corresponding to the possible projects to be funded. It has to be highlighted here that thanks to specific funding by UPPA for Cultural Heritage, an “ingénieur de recherche” (Dr Giovanna Hendel) was hired for a two- year contract to help linking and grouping together team of researchers to answer European calls (Interreg, Horizon Europe...) in the field of Cultural Heritage. Such a position is indeed quite important for the Cultural Heritage hub as Dr Hendel is connected to all researchers of the alliance. There is no doubt that this makes the activities of the CH hub much easier and efficient and that a similar post should be created for the RE and CE Hubs. It is also thanks to Dr Hendel’s initiative that a “[online padlets](https://padlet.com/giovanna_hendel/9twkmmwqspizbcih)” have been created to identify events and activities in cultural heritage

see https://padlet.com/giovanna_hendel/9twkmmwqspizbcih (fig. 2) & https://padlet.com/giovanna_hendel/q0bh0zxgz5ywwjjd .

Figure 3 : “Online padlet” for cultural heritage activities.

Such virtual “co-working spaces” are also being developed for the two other hubs in the frame of UNITA Task 4.3 led by UNIZAR and devoted to “*Energizing the territories*”. This kind of tool is indeed very important since it creates a reference tool for researchers and stakeholders in the field to easily get information on the ongoing activities and possibilities associated with the hubs. It helps, for example, to disseminate activities such as the two forthcoming CH workshops: one at UVT, on 11-12 November, to work on a cooperative project on railroads as past, present and future cultural heritage, a project that could possibly be submitted within the next Horizon call ; the other at Jaca (UNIZAR), in spring 2023, to work on a cooperative project on cultural heritage in depopulated mountain regions, as a possible submission to another European call.

3.2 Connecting research and learning

One of the aims of WP4 is to promote research activities towards undergraduate students and to provide graduated ones some support and training programs to enrich their knowledge and capacities in reaching the objectives they are pushing forward. This paragraph is devoted to the description of the environment that has been developed across UNITA constellation to ensure such missions.

3.2.1 Micro Credentials for Undergraduate Students

As the Micro credential concept of learning is still under construction for complete deployment in the curricula of the universities enrolled in UNITA, the hubs were asked to produce 3 of them, in the core thematic of the alliance. As a part of task 4.2 “*Connecting research and learning*”, deliverable D 4.4 “*Micro-credentials in the three thematic areas for bachelor students M18*” was released in April 2022. Basically, the production of the hubs in terms of Micro-credentials was decided to be limited to :

- A form describing the relevant information associated to the training program (see figure 3)
- The pedagogical material associated to the training program (slides, videos of the lectures...)
- A bank of question, that might be grouped together to form an exam, and that would assess the efficient learning of the undergraduate student.

Title of the micro-credential / Titre du micro-certificat Approaching Visual Culture		Abstract Description du cours This micro-credential targets undergraduate students and lifelong learners who wish to explore aspects of cultural heritage through the analysis of visual documents. The course is developed in 5 modules designed to present students with a range of topics related to image-making in its diverse forms: visual resources in the history of images, introduction to the history of photography, the filmic image, intangible heritage, and art education. While each module is conceived as stand-alone, overall progression is ensured through the various tasks that are assigned to the students and the overall course aims to combine more theoretical issues and hands-on or applied approaches. The lectures will be delivered in either English, French or Italian, depending on the modules. A general knowledge of history, art, cinema, and literature is essential but there is no specific prerequisite in terms of specialised knowledge.	
Person in charge of the micro-credential Responsable du micro-certificat		Learning outcomes Acquis d'apprentissage At the end of the course, students will be able to analyse visual culture in its diverse manifestations (arts, film, photography, intangible heritage). They will become familiar with the main concepts and language to appreciate, interpret, contextualise, and understand information presented through visible actions, objects, and symbols, natural or man-made.	
Full name Nom complet	Laurence Roussillon-Constanty	Aimed skills Compétences visées Understanding lectures and concepts in a specific area relating to Cultural Heritage	
E-mail address Adresse mail	Laurence.roussillon-constanty@univ-pau.fr	Prerequisites Pré-requis English, French and Italian, B2 Basic Digital skills (for browsing the Internet, collating)	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cultural Heritage <input type="checkbox"/> Circular Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Renewable Energies			
Identification code Numéro d'identification			
Awarding body (institution) Établissement émetteur	UNITA		
Country/Region of the issuer Pays de l'établissement émetteur			
Teaching language(s) Langue(s) d'enseignement	English, French, Italian		

	material and filling in the online forms)
Keywords Mots-clés	Cultural Heritage, Image, Art, Film, History, Visual Literacy, Museum, Tangible and Intangible Culture,
Period Période	Spring
Audience / Learner profile Public concerné	Bachelor Students

Participation of the learner			
<input type="checkbox"/> In person présentiel	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online distanciel	<input type="checkbox"/> Hybrid / Combined enseignement hybride	<input type="checkbox"/> Comodal enseignement co-modal
Number of ECTS credits Nombre de crédits ECTS	1		
Type of assessment Modalités de Contrôle des Connaissances (MCC)	Self-Assessment		
Teaching quality assessment / Student feedback type Mode d'évaluation de la qualité de l'enseignement	Student End of Module Questionnaire		

Figure 4 : Form describing the content and relevant information of Micro Credentials created with the support of pedagogical engineers of UPPA and USMB (example of Cultural heritage MiCr)

While the objectives that were pursued by the hubs were fulfilled (the three abovementioned pieces of material were created for the three hubs) some dissatisfaction was felt because this work was not available yet for UNITA's student as a training material in their curricula, with associated ECTS. This is the reason why USMB decided to push forward the process and to

integrate the RE MiCr into its Moodle platform, available to students for learning. Such deployment should then be encouraged and effective over the moodle platforms of the whole set of universities of the alliance and for the three hubs. However, such deployment would require important human resources as technical issues associated to incompatibilities in numerical platforms exist, and such resources do not exist in the Hubs task forces. Dealing with Micro credentials, it has also to be pointed out that the necessary accreditation by each university of these Micro Credential into their curricula should be discussed at a higher level of the WP4 as other MiCr are about to be produced by other WP of the project. These two points (deployment and accreditation) will be discussed in the next meeting of UNITA's working group devoted to Micro Credential on next 26th of October. It has to be noticed here that a list of specifications for the deployment of MiCr has been produced by a joint collaborative work of pedagogical engineers from UPPA and USMB.

3.2.2 Tools for graduate students

3.2.2.1 Summer/winter schools

With the help of financial support from Erasmus+ through its “*Blended Intensive Programs*”, it has been possible to elaborate several Summer/winter schools aiming at providing short training programs devoted to graduate students. A list is given of the program that were proposed in the core thematic of UNITA - Renewable Energy

From 11 to 15th of July 2022. 24 Students enrolled. Held in Torino.

Title : Renewable energy for the mountain territories

<https://en.unito.it/international-relations/unita-universitas-montium/unita-erasmusblended-intensive>

Figure 5: Picture of the RE summer school held at UNITO in July 2022

- Circular Economy

From 18 to 22nd of July 2022. 35 Students enrolled. Held at UBI in Covilha. Title “Circular Economy in Agri-Food Industries for Tackling Climate Change”

<https://www.ubi.pt/Evento/10963>

- Cultural Heritage

"Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) in Pays de Béarn", UPPA, 8/11/21-13/11/21

"Auteur.e.s plurilingues de langues romanes", UPPA, 31/3/22-5/4/22

1..1'ROM'POL, le polar en langue romane, un patrimoine culturel émergent', UPPA, 27/9/22-01/10/22

1..2'Arts, Environnement et Ecologie', UPPA, 5-7 October 2022

1..3'Randopat-Heritrail – Mushrooms, herbs and raw food : practices and beliefs', 7-11 November 2022

3.2.2.2 PhD cotutelle activities.

As the two French Universities involved in UNITA (UPPA and USMB) received extra-funding from *Agence Nationale de la Recherche* because of their belonging to a European University, they decided to offer 8 PhD grants to promote cotutelle activities within the Alliance in 2021.

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A call was launched to select the awarded projects and associated students. This first initiative was pursued by the other universities of the alliance in 2022. Indeed, UVT offered 9 grants (from which 5 received students candidates corresponding to the desired profiles), UBI offered 5 grants (for which 3 candidacies were positive), and UNIZAR has just launched a call for 3 grants specifically proposed to cotutelles between UNIZAR and UPPA (historical cross boundaries collaboration) and 3 grants to cotutelles between UNIZAR and other universities of the Alliance. It has to be added here that some grants received by researcher from UNITO in 2021 were also converted into UNITA cotutelles, and that such initiative is expected to be pursued in 2022. Finally, after two years since the launch of UNITA in November 2020, more than 25 PhD cotutelles projects are being carried out across UNITA. This is a very significant indication on the amount of research activities that is being carried out over UNITA hubs core thematic. Moreover, the projects launched for the co-tutelle PhDs, and the high-quality of expected outcomes, would be fundamental to trigger and sustain the establishment of research consortia within UNITA for the application to European project calls.

Cotutelles under development within the Circular Economy hub.

Title	UBI	UPPA	USMB	UVT	UNITO	UNIZAR
<i>Circular economy models in the European Union - a legal assessment from the perspective of the balance between consumers' awareness and competition law</i>		X		X		
<i>Development of sustainable nanofibrous materials from bacterial polymers and biobased waterborne latex</i>	X	X				
<i>Development of enabling technologies for regional residual biomass valorization in a context of circular economy</i>			X		X	
<i>Circular economy of textile dyeing effluents</i>	X				X	
<i>Valorization of viticultural waste: novel methodological approaches to exploit anticancer properties of bioactive compounds</i>	X		X			
<i>Optimization of biohydrogen generation from agro-food wastewaters by combination of dark fermentation and photofermentation</i>	X					X
<i>Challenges in Corporate Reporting Concerning Circular Economy</i>				X	X	

Cotutelles under development within the Renewable Energy hub.

Title	UBI	UPPA	USMB	UVT	UNITO	UNIZAR
Synthesis of stable Hole Transporting Materials (HTMs) for emerging hybrid photovoltaics		X			X	
Modeling rain interarrival times and rain depths		X			X	
<u>Energy transformation and integration systems - Energy carriers</u> , “Distributed solar energy source in a mixed local renewable energy system in response of energy demand in mixed urban - rural attractive territory			X			X
DESCOPE-NANO : Durable and Efficient Solar Cells COmbining PErovskite and NANOcrystals			X			X
Distributed solar energy source in a mixed local renewable energy system in response of energy demand in mixed urban - rural attractive territory			X		X	
Development and Optimisation of a Trigeration System based on Adsorption Machine Technology	X	X				
<i>Conventional Energy vs. Renewable Energy. The Impact of Turbulences</i>		X		X		

Cotutelles under development within the Cultural Heritage hub.

Title	UBI	UPPA	USMB	UVT	UNITO	UNIZAR
On the circulation of religious literature between Italy and France in the 16th century : the case of the first French translation of Dante’s Paradise (manuscripts Paris, BnF, naf 4119 and 4530)			x		X	

Vers la construction d'un musée virtuel UNITA Montis : mise en valeur et médiation du patrimoine historique et culturel dans un environnement plurilingue.		X			X	
<u>!La gestion du patrimoine culturel immatériel : Une étude de cas comparative entre le Pays de Béarn (France) et le Banat (Roumanie)</u>		x		x		
Mythocritical Approach to the Son Figure in Contemporary French and Francophone Literature				x	x	
Carnival(s): Tradition and (Re)Invention. Comparative study: Banat Region and Pays de Béarn		x		x		
Gender Equality beyond Preferentialism. Towards a Comparison Virtue-Based Engagement Ethics in Organizations				x	x	
Schools as Learning Organizations for inclusive Education				X	X	

A political assessment of the intensity of this cotutelle activity was also given by the signature of a “protocol” aiming at describing the rules prevailing for UNITA cotutelles by UNITA governance board organized by UVT in Timisoara on the 2nd of June 2022. See Figure 5, and Appendix.

Figure 6: Signature by UNITA governance board of the “UNITA’s cotutelle protocol” 2nd of June. Timisoara.

3.2.2.3 Network of Doctoral schools.

As UNITA’s cotutelle protocol was about to be signed by UNITA’s governance board, UPPA also proposed that a network composed by the head of the different doctoral schools of UNITA be created. Such proposal was acknowledged by the governance board, with the main objectives to share good practices, promote common values on training program devoted to PhD students and finally develop the feeling of belonging to the alliance. These objectives were lately derived in the following missions

- Develop the understanding of the way doctoral programs are being carried out in the different universities of the alliance.
- Organize common events (“*doctoriales*”) between PhD Students of the alliance (at least with UNITA’s cotutelle ones) to promote and foster the feeling of a common belonging
- Share good practices for hiring PhD Students (Important for Label HRS4R)
- Ensure link between PhD programs and Thematic hubs activities - Promote and help PhD students’ mobility across the alliance.
- Create teams project aiming at answering MSCA doctoral program COFUND call in February 2023.

-
- Promote elaboration of joint common PhD programs across UNITA (which is indeed one of the sub task of WP4 : Sub Task 4.2.3 “*Enhancing links among the UNITA PhD programs*”

First meeting of this network was organized online on the 19th of July was the first meeting devoted to the preparation of a proposal for raising a COFUND project in the field of cultural heritage took place online on the 15th of September 2022.

We can then be very confident on the ability of this network to promote, encourage and help UNITA thematic hubs in the development of their activities regarding doctoral studies.:

3.2.2.4 Possible training activities

As it was described above, the graduate activities are numerous within UNITA. It seems important as well to add that Re-UNITA is a leading force in the development of such activities. Indeed, and as three significant examples one can say that:

- A database for shared infrastructures (and a corresponding agreement ruling their use) has been developed in the frame of Re_U WP4 led by UNIZAR. Such database offers a very important support for Doctoral students and researchers that might need specific scientific tools or pieces of art, not available in the university they belong to.
- A program promoting entrepreneurship has been developed in the frame of Re_U WP5 led by UBI (Spin-Off forum on the 22nd of October and training day devoted to entrepreneurship on the 19th of October both organized by UNIZAR)
- A program promoting and training to open science is being developed in the frame of Re_U WP6 led by UVT with activities related to open science led by USMB. Finally, with its R&I thematic Hubs and constellation, UNITA is able to propose the following list of activities to its graduate and/or PhD Students (Table 1).

Title of the tool	Description of the tool	Terms and conditions of access	Starting date	More information
Short physical mobility	Mobility between 5 and 30 days. // Need to have a formal agreement with the host university at the doctoral level and in the doctoral student's field of study // Attention : Cotutelle case : A stay included in the cotutelle agreement is not possible	Have a mobility project for research // check Erasmus agreements // apply for a grant //attention with UNITA-cotutelle (ex : cotutelle UPPA/UNITO : you can't have a financial Erasmus support to go to UNITO)	whenever you want	
Virtual mobility	Attend a distance learning course in one of the universities of the UNITA Alliance (in the local university language or in English) // synchronous, asynchronous or hybrid courses	Answer a questionnaire launched before each semester (June for the fall semester and November for the spring semester) // Compare the course schedule with your program // Register at the university of the course (guided by UNITA managers)	Each semester (registration 2-3 months before)	https://organisation.univ-pau.fr/fr/grands-projets/unita/mobilites-virtuelles.html
Hybrid mobility // Thematic schools	The academic year is punctuated by Blended Intensive Programs (BIP). Spend between 5 and 30 days in one of the partner or associated universities to learn more about a specific theme (art-ecology, renewable energy, etc. (Erasmus financial support)	Answer a form launched 2 months before a BIP. // Complete the Kit de Mobilité // Complete a Learning Agreement with your research director signature // Apply for a grant (guided by UNITA manager and Grant manager)	all along the academic year (registration 2 months before)	https://formation.univ-pau.fr/fr/catalogue/summer-winter-schools.html
Rural experience	Conduct a rural immersion experience in a UNITA partner country during the summer (eco-museum, geopark, etc.)	Answer a form launched in february/march for the next summer. // Apply for an internship in Limesurvey plateforme // Apply for a grant (guided by UNITA managers and grant manager)	summer (registration 5 months before)	https://organisation.univ-pau.fr/fr/grands-projets/unita/mobilites-rurales-urm-et-uri-stages.html
Intercomprehension courses	To acquire the tools and strategies to understand other Romance languages (French, Spanish, Portuguese, Italian, Romanian) // hybrid courses	Answer a form launched 1 month before each semester	Each semester (registration 1 month before)	https://organisation.univ-pau.fr/fr/grands-projets/unita.html
European citizenship workshop	Workshops around the feeling of European citizenship (2 hours meeting in november/december)	Answer a call launched by email few weeks before the workshops	november/december (registration few weeks before)	https://organisation.univ-pau.fr/fr/grands-projets/unita.html
Student Assembly	Three students involved in the governance of the alliance during one year. They will represent the university in two decisional boards: the Governance Board (GB) and the Quality Assurance Board (QAB).	Answer a call launched by email to candidate to the position		UNITA Universitat Montium : alliance d'universités de cinq pays européens - Université - Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour (UPPA) (univ-pau.fr)
Open Science trainings	Cycle of workshops/trainings dedicated to all dimensions of open science (data management, open access publications, etc.)	To be defined	November 2022 - August 2024	To be defined
Networked of shared research infrastructures & resources	Facilities and funding to use equipment/resources at another UNITA university	To be defined	November 2022 - August 2024	Catalogue : https://reunitaresearchinfrastructure.i3a.es/
Weekly online research seminars	Research seminar by a UNITA researcher, online, duration 30 minutes	Open to all students, PhD, researchers, upon registration.	October 2022 - no limit	Information online : https://www.univ-unita.eu
Trainings and workshops on entrepreneurship	Various events are organized within Re-UNITA, promoting entrepreneurship and the links between research activities and private sector. Innovative tools will be used as a proof-of-concept program to enhance creativity among PhD Students and other researchers	Some events will be open to the whole community, others will require the creation of mixed teams composed of PhD students from different UNITA universities.	September 2022 - August 2024	Information online : https://www.univ-unita.eu
Living labs and open-seminars	Events planned with the Public authorities and NGOs to enhance the share of practices on problematics identified	To be presented later	February 2023 - August 2024	Information online : https://www.univ-unita.eu

Table 1: list of activities offered to UNITA's graduate and/or PhD Students.

3.3 Promoting research towards academic community and territories

The main goal of the activities of UNITA R&I thematic hubs is to help its territories in the development of its socio-economic activities, by including research results into their daily operation. This is an important ambition, that requires, at first, to make the connection between the hubs and these territories and their stakeholders. This paragraph is devoted to the description of what has been developed in the frame of UNITA to ensure such a connection.

3.3.1 Research Cartography

In the early months of UNITA and in the frame of Task 4.1 led by UPPA a call for expression of interest was launched to map all the activities that were carried out over the alliance in its core thematic. The activities were grouped together in a “[research cartography](#)” (See Deliverable 4.1.1 A cartography of research in the three thematic areas). This cartography

has significantly evolved since its creation thanks to the addition of the activities of UAPs and to its dissemination to the whole world. Indeed, it has been asked to all contributors to acknowledge about publication of the personal information that were recorded in the database. By now the “[research cartography](#)” contains 649 projects, with detailed information on associated contributors, what constitutes a reference database for researchers and stakeholders to identify possible collaborations among the alliance.

Figure 7: “[research cartography](#)” containing a description of the projects in the core thematic of the alliance

3.3.2 Research Newsletter and Brochure.

In the frame of Re-UNITA Work Package 2 led by USMB and under the daily work of UBI, a monthly newsletter devoted to research activities being carried out in the hubs has been published since March 2022. This newsletter is based on a recurring template which is described below.

EDITORIAL	Introduction from Vice-Rector for Research Small presentation/article focusing on a specific date, according with UNITA/Re-UNITA goal
CH, CE, RE	Ongoing research project related to each topic.
PhD Student of the month	PhD Student developing research on CH, CE or RE, proposed by each university.
Women in CH/CE/RE	A woman researcher selected by each partner (interview).
HIGHLIGHTS	Flexible section to highlight remarkable outcomes on each research topic.

Editorial

The inaugural issue of the Re-UNITA Newsletter is out!

Published in this electronic format and with a quarterly periodicity, the Newsletter will highlight the research undertaken within the UNITA and Re-UNITA community, namely on the three central topics of Cultural Heritage, Circular Economy and Renewable Energies. In this and following issues we will have contributions of the alliance's University members covering all these thematic areas.

This first issue highlights the UPA's ESR&D(E) research project on Renewable Energies. It investigates the efficient and reliable direct current electricity distribution at home and offices, aiming to significantly increase the energy efficiency in buildings and, consequently, approach the ambitious objectives defined by European Directives, concerning energy policy. On Circular Economy, and from UPPA, comes the "ARISE2026" project. The proposed research envisages recycling plastic packaging and converting into high-performance materials, aligned with the environmental challenge of developing bioremediation, competition and their processing. The UPA's highlight on Cultural Heritage shows their interdisciplinary approach in interaction with indigenous communities and reexamining the notion of authenticity associated with heritage (Alpine pastures, habitats, the Chavot CCR).

The Newsletter also is enriched by the sections dedicated to female researchers (BPPA, Evelyn Gayard interview) and Ph.D. student of the month (BPPA, Cynthia Faria -winner of the Local Three Minutes Thesis competition).

Finally, March is a month rich in several commemorative dates, to mention the Women International Day (8th), the International Day of Forests (21st) and the World Water Day (22nd). The Re-UNITA research, directly or indirectly, reports to those important worldwide celebrations, and could make the difference for a better and more sustainable world.

I hope you enjoy reading about UNITA/Re-UNITA researchers and their respective research fields!

Stefo Scacco
Vice-Rector for Research
University of Savoie-Tarbes

Cultural Heritage

Circular Economy

Renewable Energies

Figure 8: Template use for the elaboration of the monthly research newsletter (left)
First edition of the newsletter (March 2022, right)

Up to now, 7 newsletters have been published.

Promotion of research activities within UNITA is also achieved with the Brochure prepared in the Frame of Re-UNITA WP7 led by UPPA. This brochure has been published in the 5 roman languages of the alliance. A reproduction of its English version is provided below.

How to contact us ?
reunita@univ-pau.fr
<http://www.univ-unita.eu>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 710101830

Drawing a common research and innovation strategy among the UNITA Alliance

Re-UNITA Research for UNITA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 710101830

<http://www.univ-unita.eu>

Figure 9: Brochure describing research activities within UNITA and possible connection with stakeholders.

3.3.3 . UNITA Weekly talks

In order to raise the feeling of belonging of the researchers to the alliance and to promote UNITA core thematic activities to surrounding territories, WP4 Coordinating committee decide to launch an *online seminar series* entitled “UNITA Weekly Talk”. It was also a possible way to increase the level of Indicator Ind.4.2. “*Number of students taking part in research-driven learning*” (2500). The first edition of these online conferences was delivered on the 12th of May 2022 and was given by Mr Stjin Deauré from the Directorate General for Research and Innovation (DG-RTD) at the European commission and by Prof Jose Antonio Mayoral Murillo, Rector of UNIZAR and of UNITA (See figure below).

Figure 10: “Flyer” describing the online presentation.

With the help of technical services of UPPA, a MS Teams environment was developed to make possible interaction of the audience with the presenter and to record the presentation for possible off-line replay of the seminar (see figure below)

Figure 11: UNITA weekly online research presentation for replay of the weekly talks.

A specific platform was also developed to register the audience attending the presentations, by university of origin, discipline, and profile (Undergraduate, graduate or PhD Students,

researchers, lecturers, other staff and stakeholders). Since the 12th of May, 12 talks have been delivered (every Thursday from noon to 12.30 CET) with an overall registration of 536 persons (see figure below).

Figure 12: Overall registration level for the past UNITA weekly talks.

Given the fact that the 10 UNITA universities hold almost 200 000 students and 15 000 staff members, the participation to the online series of seminars can be considered low to very low. It has also to be underlined that student participation to the seminars is very low. Nevertheless, further analysis can be developed which shows that the satisfaction barometer for the events is quite high, which is very positive and encouraging to find out mechanisms that would increase the number of attendees.

Figure 13: Profile of registered attendants to the seminar and satisfaction barometer. The extra low participation might be attributed to communication issues. Indeed, this online seminar series is still “young” and has probably not been disseminated enough among training programs of UNITA (undergraduate, graduate, doctoral), research institutions (laboratories, technical centers...) and stakeholders (companies, territories, NGOs...). This represents a challenge for the year to come to increase the participation of UNITA community to these online research seminars.

3.3.4 Liaison services : intensive repository.

The final tool that has been developed to link UNITA to its territories is the liaison service. It corresponds to one of the sub-task of Task 4.3 “*Energizing the territories*” led by UNIZAR. Basically, this liaison service is a place where research internship positions coming from academia or stakeholders are offered to UNITA Students. Such a liaison service has been built very recently so it remains too early to give information on its actual use. The liaison service can be accessed through UNITA web site under sub category “Research”.

Internships

UNITA connects universities, students, territories, and local stakeholders to generate participative frameworks for innovation and applied research and develop rural and mountain regions.

For students, UNITA offers innovation and research internships in companies, research centres, or institutions mainly focused on the three areas of renewable energy, circular economy, and cultural heritage.

The internships will allow students to participate and experience knowledge transfer processes and rural development dynamics up close.

[More information »](#)

Figure 14: Picture of the web page developed to access UNITA Liaison Service.

4 An ambition for a strategic R&I plan in the three thematic.

As it has been shown in the past paragraphs, the R&I hubs have already been very productive and numerous results have been obtained. Even though the people involved in the task forces are not numerous enough, there is evidence that research communities have been created and the feeling of belonging to the project has been realized.

Given these first results obtained we feel it is now possible to draw an ambition as a “*A strategic five-year R&I plan in the three thematic areas*”.

During these first two years, UNITA and Re-UNITA have made it possible to define a common research and innovation ambition: the alliance wishes to position itself at the European level on themes specific to rural and mountain territories which are the DNA of this alliance. The three initial core thematic will be extended to other relevant themes, under consideration with the organisation of research matching events (Torino, 22/10/26).

Emerging and existing thematic will be led by an out-of-walls European Research and Innovation Institute (ER2I), built as an extension of the hubs as soon as a critical mass of sounding research expertise, funding and resources are reached.

These ER2Is would then be reference and leading organisation, with international recognition on their field of knowledge and connected to the territories to which the universities of the alliance belong at the same time.

Given the major climatic and societal challenges that we will all need to face in the coming years, these ER2I could be an answer to address and solve the issues raised by the necessary changes in our way of leaving, namely by:

- contributing to the development of a common scientific identity for the alliance, shared by staff and students, at least at graduate level.
- increasing the visibility of UNITA's specific themes, both internally and with regard to the socio-economic and cultural partners in its territories.
- giving access to all the partners' facilities, which places researchers in favourable conditions to push back the frontiers of knowledge.
- encouraging interdisciplinary, cross-disciplinary approaches that make it possible to grasp the full complexity of societal issues and thus constitute the crucible for cross-cutting high-level research.
- being the ideal places to encourage and develop open innovation with multiple stake holders.

-
- having the task, within their scientific area of intervention, of strengthening the research-training link through the implementation of a networked graduate programme,
 - being part of the master's-doctorate continuum and supported by innovative teaching practices based on training through research.
 - being key elements in the attractiveness of UNITA to young talent, in particular.
 - being the privileged interlocutors of the socio-economic and cultural partners present in the territories of the alliance with whom they interact to develop joint research programmes.

The IR2I evaluation by the states to which their universities belong and by the European Research Area could highlight their level of excellence, helping them to get recurring and long-term funding from both ERA and constituting institutions, and to win funding from Regional, National and European calls for projects with connected stakeholders. Such institutes would also be ideal organisations to disseminate, explain and give benefits of their results to the citizen and socio-economic environment composing their territories.

5 Conclusion

WP4 R&I Hubs are expected to play a very important role in the promotion of UNITA and in the assistance to local territories to empower them in reducing inequalities between core and non-central regions through sustainable development. After one year of operation, numerous results have been obtained by the R&I Hubs, showing their efficiency to address some of the issues for which they have been built. The ER2I will be the ideal place to build efficient and strategic networks with high potential for Horizon Europe and international calls applications. The connection with stakeholders and territories is not completely effective yet but this will be the main goal of the year to come, with still important efforts, involvement and commitment of the task forces that are the real actors and contributors to the hubs.

The strategy we wish to put in place for their future is to transform them into European Research and Innovation Institutes which would be places of excellence for the development of scientific activities and projects addressing societal challenges allowing the development of the core territories of UNITA.

Appendix

<p>Protocol for the co-supervised doctoral research thesis between partners of the UNITA Alliance</p>	<p>Protocole de cotutelle de thèse entre les partenaires de l'Alliance UNITA</p>	<p>Protocollo per cotutela di tesi tra i partner dell'Alleanza UNITA</p>	<p>Protocolo de cooperação em cotutela para a supervisão conjunta da tese de doutoramento entre os parceiros da Aliança UNITA</p>	<p>Protocol de cotuteliã pentru studii doctorale între partenerii Alianței UNITA</p>	<p>Protocolo para la cotutela de tesis doctorales entre los socios de la Alianza UNITA</p>
<p>Between The Università degli Studi di Torino, located at Via Verdi, 8 - 10124 Torino (Italy), represented by its Rector, Mr. Stefano GEUNA, hereinafter referred to as "Unito"</p>	<p>Entre L'Université de Turin, située Via Verdi, 8 - 10124 Torino (Italie), représentée par son Recteur, Monsieur Stefano GEUNA, ci-après désignée par « Unito »</p>	<p>Tra L'Università degli Studi di Torino, con sede in Via Verdi, 8 - 10124 Torino (Italia), rappresentata dal Rettore, Stefano Geuna, di seguito indicata come "Unito"</p>	<p>Entre A Universitat degli Studi di Torino, con sede em Via Verdi, 8 - 10124 Torino (Itàlia), representada pelo seu Rector, Stefano GEUNA, designada por « Unito »</p>	<p>Între Universitã degli Studi di Torino, cu sediul în Via Verdi, nr. 8 - 10124 Torino (Italia), reprezentatã prin Rector, Dl. Stefano GEUNA, denumitã în continuare „Unito”</p>	<p>Entre La Università degli Studi di Torino, situada en Via Verdi, 8 - 10124 Torino (Italia), representada por su Rector, el Sr. Stefano GEUNA, en lo sucesivo "Unito"</p>
<p>And The Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour, located 27 Rue Marcoz, BP 1104, 73011 Chambléry Cedex (France), registered with INSEE under Siret no. 196 402 515 00270, and assigned the APE activity code 8542Z, represented by its President, Mr Laurent BORDES hereinafter referred to as "UPPA"</p>	<p>Et L'Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour, située avenue de l'université, BP 576, 64012 Pau Cedex (France), enregistrée par l'INSEE sous le n° Siret 196 402 515 00270, sous le code APE 8542Z, représentée par son Président, Monsieur Laurent BORDES, ci-après désignée par l' « UPPA »</p>	<p>L' Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour, con sede in avenue de l'université, BP 576, 64012 Pau Cedex (Francia), registrata dall'INSEE con numero Siret 196 402 515 00270 sotto il codice APE 8542Z, rappresentata dal Presidente Laurent BORDES di seguito indicata come «UPPA»</p>	<p>E A Universitã de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour, com sediã em avenue de l'universitã, BP 576, 64012 Pau Cedex (Frangã), registrada pelo l'INSEE com o n° Siret 196 402 515 00270, e o cãdigo APE 8542Z, representada pelo seu Presidente, Laurent BORDES, designada por « UPPA »</p>	<p>și L'universitã de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour, cu sediul în Avenue de l'universitã, BP 576, 64012 Pau Cedex (Frangã), înregistratã la INSEE cu nr. Siret 196 402 515 00270, cod APE 8542Z, reprezentatã prin Rector, Dl. Laurent BORDES, denumitã în continuare „UPPA”</p>	<p>Y La Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour, con sede en avenue de l'université, BP 576, 64012 Pau Cedex (Francia), inscrita en el INSEE con el número Siret 196 402 515 00270, y con el código de actividad APE 8542Z, representada por su Presidente, el Sr. Laurent BORDES en lo sucesivo "UPPA"</p>
<p>And The Université de Savoie Mont Blanc, located 27 Rue Marcoz, BP 1104, 73011 Chambléry Cedex (France), registered with INSEE under Siret no. 197 308 588 00015, and assigned the APE activity code 8542Z, represented by its president, Mr Philippe GALEZ, hereinafter referred to as "USMB "</p>	<p>Et L'Université de Savoie Mont Blanc, située 27 Rue Marcoz, BP 1104, 73011 Chambléry Cedex (France), enregistrée par l'INSEE sous le n° Siret 197 308 588 00015, sous le code APE 8542Z représentée par son président, Monsieur Philippe GALEZ, ci-après désignée par « USMB »</p>	<p>L'Université de Savoie Mont Blanc, con sede in 27 Rue Marcoz, BP 1104, 73011 Chambléry Cedex (Francia), registrada dall'INSEE con numero Siret 197 308 588 00015 sotto il codice APE 8542Z, rappresentata dal Presidente Philippe GALEZ di seguito indicata come «USMB»</p>	<p>E A Universitã de Savoie Mont Blanc, com sediã em 27 Rue Marcoz, BP 1104, 73011 Chambléry Cedex (Frangã), registrada pelo l'INSEE com o n° Siret 197 308 588 00015, sous le code APE 8542Z, representada pelo seu Presidente, Philippe GALEZ, designada por « USMB »</p>	<p>și L'universitã de Savoie Mont Blanc, cu sediul în 27 Rue Marcoz, BP 1104, 73011 Chambléry Cedex (Frangã), înregistratã la INSEE cu nr. Siret 197 308 588 00015, cod APE 8542Z, reprezentatã prin Rector, Dl. Philippe GALEZ, denumitã în continuare „USMB”</p>	<p>Y La Université de Savoie Mont Blanc, con sede en 27 Rue Marcoz, BP 1104, 73011 Chambléry Cedex (Francia), inscrita en el INSEE con el número Siret 197 308 588 00015, y con el código de actividad APE 8542Z, representada por su presidente, el Sr. Philippe GALEZ, en lo sucesivo "USMB "</p>
<p>And The Universidad de Zaragoza, located calle Pedro Cerbuna, 12, 50009, Zaragoza, (Spain), represented by its Rector Mr José Antonio MAYORAL MURILLO, hereinafter referred to as "UNIZAR"</p>	<p>Et L'Université de Zaragoza, ayant son siège social calle Pedro Cerbuna, 12, 50009, Zaragoza, (Espagne) représentée par son Recteur Monsieur José Antonio MAYORAL MURILLO, ci-après désignée par l' « UNIZAR ».</p>	<p>L'Universidad de Zaragoza, con sede in calle Pedro Cerbuna, 12, 50009, Zaragoza, (Españal) representada dal Rettore José Antonio MAYORAL MURILLO, di seguito indicata come «UNIZAR»</p>	<p>E A Universidad de Zaragoza, con sede em calle Pedro Cerbuna, 12, 50009, Zaragoza, (Españal) representada pelo seu Rector José Antonio MAYORAL MURILLO, designada por « UNIZAR ».</p>	<p>și Universidad de Zaragoza, cu sediul în calle Pedro Cerbuna, 12, 50009, Zaragoza, (Españal) reprezentatã prin Rector, Dl. José Antonio MAYORAL MURILLO, denumitã în continuare „UNIZAR”.</p>	<p>Y La Universidad de Zaragoza, con sede en la calle Pedro Cerbuna, 12, 50009, Zaragoza, (Españal), representada por su Rector D. José Antonio MAYORAL MURILLO, en lo sucesivo "UNIZAR"</p>
<p>and</p>	<p>Et</p>	<p>E</p>	<p>E</p>	<p>și</p>	<p>Y</p>

<p>The Universidade da Beira Interior, located Convento de Sto. António, 6201-001 Covilhã, (Portugal), represented by its Rector Mr Mário Uno BARBATA RAPOSO. hereinafter referred to as "UBI"</p>	<p>L'Université de Beira Interior, située Convento de Sto. António, 6201-001 Covilhã, (Portugal), représentée par son Recteur Monsieur Mário Uno BARBATA RAPOSO. ci-après désignée par l'« UBI »</p>	<p>L'Universidade da Beira Interior, com sede em Convento de Sto. António, 6201-001 Covilhã, (Portugal), representada dal Rector Mário Uno BARBATA RAPOSO di seguito indicata come «UBI»</p>	<p>A Universidade da Beira Interior, com sede em Convento de Santo António 6201-001 Covilhã, (Portugal), representada pelo seu Rector Mário Uno BARBATA RAPOSO, designada por « UBI »</p>	<p>Universitatea da Beira Interior, cu sediul în Convento de Sto. António, 6201-001 Covilhã, (Portugalia), reprezentată prin Rector, Dl. Mário Uno BARBATA RAPOSO, denumită în continuare „UBI”</p>	<p>La Universidade da Beira Interior, con sede en el Convento de Sto. António, 6201-001 Covilhã, (Portugal), representada por su Rector D. Mário Uno BARBATA RAPOSO, en lo sucesivo "UBI"</p>
<p>The Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara, located Bd. Vasile Pârvan nr. 4, Timișoara, cod postal 300223, județul Timi (Romania), represented by its Rector, Mr Marien Gabriel PIŢTEA, hereinafter referred to as "UVT"</p>	<p>L'Universit de Vest din Timișoara, situe Bd. Vasile Pârvan nr. 4, Timișoara cod postal 300223, județul Timi (Roumaniei), reprezentte par son Recteur, Monsieur Marien Gabriel PIŢTEA, ci-aprs dsigne par l'« UVT »</p>	<p>L'Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara, con sede in Bd. Vasile Pârvan nr. 4, Timișoara, cod postal 300223, județul Timi (Romania), reprezentata dal Rector Marien Gabriel PIŢTEA</p>	<p>A Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara, con sede em Bd. Vasile Pârvan nr. 4, Timișoara, cod postal 300223, județul Timi (Romania), reprezentada pelo seu Rector, Marien Gabriel PIŢTEA, designada por « UVT »</p>	<p>Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara, cu sediul în Timișoara, Bd. Vasile Pârvan nr. 4, cod postal 300223, județul Timiș (Romania), reprezentat prin Rector, Dl. Marien Gabriel PIŢTEA, denumit în continuare „UVT”</p>	<p>La Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara, con sede en Bd. Vasile Pârvan nr. 4, Timișoara, cod postal 300223, județul Timi (Romania), representada por su Rector, el Sr. Marien Gabriel PIŢTEA, en lo sucesivo, "UVT"</p>
<p>Unito, UPPA, USMB, UNIZAR, UBI and UVT may be referred to individually as the "Parties" and collectively as the "Parties".</p>	<p>L'Unito, l'UPPA, l'USMB, l'UNIZAR, l'UBI et l'UVT peuvent tre ci-aprs individuellement dsignes par la « Partie » et collectivement par les « Parties ».</p>	<p>Unito, UPPA, USMB, UNIZAR, UBI and UVT possono essere di seguito designate individualmente come la "Parte" e collettivamente come le "Parti".</p>	<p>A Unito, a UPPA, a USMB, a UNIZAR, a UBI e a UVT podem ser individualmente designadas pela « Parte » e colectivamente pelas « Partes ».</p>	<p>Unito, UPPA, USMB, UNIZAR, UBI și UVT pot fi denumite, în continuare, în mod individual „partea” și, în mod colectiv, „partile”.</p>	<p>Unito, UPPA, USMB, UNIZAR, UBI y UVT pueden ser referidas individualmente como la "Parte" y colectivamente como las "Partes".</p>
<p>- Considered the UNITRA – Universitas Montium project (Erasmus+ - EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES EPP-EUR-UNIV-2020) (hereinafter referred as the "Project");</p> <p>- Considered the Consortium Agreement for the implementation of the Erasmus "UNITRA – Universitas Montium" project (hereinafter referred to as the "Consortium Agreement"); referenced UPPA CONT-2021-0091);</p> <p>- In accordance with the quality requirements of the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education regulating organization and management of mobility;</p> <p>- In accordance with the requirements of the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers and in compliance with the procedures of each institution involved in the HRSAR approach;</p>	<p>-Vu le projet UNITRA – Universitas Montium (Erasmus+ - UNIVERSITES EUROPENNES PPE-EUR-UNIV-2020) (ci-aprs dnomm le « Projet »);</p> <p>-Vu l'accord de consortium pour la mise en uvre du projet Erasmus « UNITRA – Universitas Montium » (ci-aprs dnomm l'« Accord de Consortium »); rfrenc UPPA CONT-2021-0091;</p> <p>-Conformment aux exigences de qualit de la Charte Erasmus pour l'enseignement et la gestion de la mobilit;</p> <p>-Conformment aux exigences de la Charte Europenne du chercheur et du Code de conduite pour le recrutement des chercheurs et dans le respect des procdures de chaque tablissement engag dans HRSAR;</p>	<p>-Visto il progetto UNITRA – Universitas Montium (Erasmus+ - EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES EPP-EUR-UNIV-2020) (di seguito denominato il "Progetto");</p> <p>-Visto l'accordo di Consorzio per l'implementazione del Progetto Erasmus «UNITRA – Universitas Montium (di seguito denominato l'«Accordo di Consorzio»)», registrato come UPPA CONT-2021-0091;</p> <p>- In conformit ai requisiti di qualit della Carta Erasmus per l'Istruzione Superiore che regola l'organizzazione e la gestione della mobilit;</p> <p>- In conformit ai requisiti della Carta Europea dei Ricercatori e al Codice di Condotta per il Reclutamento dei Ricercatori e nel rispetto delle procedure di ciascuna istituzione coinvolta dall'approccio HRSAR;</p>	<p>- Considerando o projeto UNITRA – Universitas Montium (Erasmus+ - UNIVERSITIES EUROPEENNES PPE-EUR-UNIV-2020) (abaixo designado por «Projeto »);</p> <p>- Considerando o acordo de consrcio para a implementao do projeto Erasmus «UNITRA – Universitas Montium (abaixo designado por «Acordo de Consrcio»)», referenciado na UBI sob o n. 1211151;</p> <p>-De acordo com os requisitos de qualidade da Carta Erasmus para o Ensino Superior que rege a organizao e gesto da mobilitade;</p> <p>-De acordo com os requisitos da Carta Europeia do Investigador e do Cdigo de Conduta para o Recrutamento de Investigadores e em conformidade com os procedimentos de cada instituio envolvida no HRSAR;</p>	<p>-Avnd in vedere proiectul UNITRA – Universitas Montium (Erasmus+ - UNIVERSITIES EUROPEENNES PPE-EUR-UNIV-2020) (denumit in continuare „proiectul”);</p> <p>-Avnd in vedere Acordul de parteneriat pentru implementarea proiectului Erasmus „UNITRA – Universitatii Montium” (denumit in continuare „Acord de parteneriat”), cu numral de referin UPPA CONT-2021-0091;</p> <p>-In conformitate cu cerinele calitative din Carta Erasmus pentru învățămntul superior ce reglementeaz organizația și gestionarea mobilitilor;</p> <p>-In conformitate cu cerințele calitative din Carta European a cercetatorilor și Codul de conduit pentru recrutarea cercetatorilor, și cu respectarea procedurilor fiecrei instituiii implicate în abordarea HRSAR;</p>	<p>Considerado el proyecto UNITRA -Universitas Montium (Erasmus+ - UNIVERSIDADES EUROPEAS EPP-EUR-UNIV-2020) (en adelante, referido como el "Proyecto");</p> <p>Considerado el Acuerdo de Consorcio para la ejecucin del proyecto Erasmus "UNITRA -Universitas Montium" (en lo sucesivo referido como el "Acuerdo de Consorcio", con referencia UPPA CONT-2021-0091);</p> <p>-De conformidad con los requisitos de calidad de la Carta Erasmus de Educacin Superior, que regula la organizacin y gestin de la movilidad;</p> <p>-De conformidad con los requisitos de la Carta Europea del Investigador y el Cdigo de Conducta para la Contratacin de Investigadores y en cumplimiento de los procedimientos de cada institucin que participa en el enfoque HRSAR;</p>
<p>The Parties agree to place this agreement, hereinafter referred as the "Protocol" in accordance with the provisions of the Consortium Agreement cited before, governing in particular confidentiality, IP and exploitation conditions.</p>	<p>en consequence, les Parties conviennent de placer le prsent contrat, ci-aprs dnomm le « protocole » sous le rgime de l'Accord de Consortium dfini ci-avant, rgissant en particulier la confidentialit, la proprit intellectuelle et les conditions d'exploitation.</p>	<p>le Parti concordano di stipulare il presente accordo, di seguito denominato il "Protocollo", in conformit con quanto previsto dal succitato Accordo di Consorzio, che disciplina, in particolare, la propriet intellettuale e le condizioni di sfruttamento.</p>	<p>as Partes Zigtore mzmem assinar este contrato, doravante denominado «Protocolo» no mbito do Contrato de Consrcio acima definido, regendo em particular a confidencialidade, propriedade intelectual e condies de operacionalizao.</p>	<p>Partile convin s supun acest acord, denumit in continuare „protocol”, prevndur  Acordului de parteneriat menționat anterior, care reglementeaz în special confidențibilitatea, drepturile de proprietate intelectuală și condițiile de utilizare a rezultatelor cercetării.</p>	<p>las Partes acuerdan celebrar el presente acuerdo, en lo sucesivo denominado el "Protocolo", de conformidad con las disposiciones del Acuerdo de Consorzio antes citado, que regulan, en particular, las condiciones de confidencialidad, propiedad intelectual y explotacin.</p>

<p>Preamble:</p> <p>This protocol for the co-supervised doctoral research thesis, prepared within the framework of the European Universities Initiative, aims to promote collaboration and mobility at the doctoral level between the member universities of the UNiTA-Universitas Montium Alliance. The institutions involved in the Protocol have the common goal of encouraging and developing scientific cooperation in the training of researchers and promoting the mobility of doctoral students from their respective institutions.</p> <p>By entering into this Protocol, each university commits to admitting the doctoral candidate to doctoral training at its respective institution, to provide joint supervision and to fulfil their obligations towards the doctoral candidate during the period of co-tutelle.</p> <p>Each partner institution also commits to awarding a full doctoral degree to the doctoral candidate upon fulfilment of the requirements.</p> <p>The Parties agree to establish this protocol of international co-supervision of a thesis within the UNiTA Alliance, which specifies the terms of the collaboration. It is concluded in mutual understanding and respect of each university's national legislation and local regulations, on the understanding that :</p>	<p>Préambule :</p> <p>Ce protocole de cotutelle, préparé dans le cadre de l'initiative des universités européennes, vise à promouvoir la collaboration et la mobilité au niveau du doctorat entre les universités membres de l'Alliance UNiTA-Universitas Montium. Les institutions concernées par le Protocole ont pour but commun d'encourager et de développer la coopération scientifique dans la formation de chercheurs et de favoriser la mobilité des doctorants(e)s de leurs institutions respectives.</p> <p>En conduisant ce Protocole, chaque université s'engage à admettre le candidat au doctorat à la formation doctorale dans son institution respective, à assurer une supervision conjointe et à remplir ses obligations envers le candidat au doctorat pendant la période de cotutelle.</p> <p>Chaque institution partenaire s'engage également à délivrer le diplôme de doctorat à part entière au candidat au doctorat s'il remplit les conditions requises par chaque établissement concerné.</p> <p>Les Parties conviennent de la mise en place de ce protocole de cotutelle internationale de thèse au sein de l'Alliance UNiTA, qui précise les termes de la collaboration. Le Protocole est conclu dans la compréhension et le respect mutuels de la législation nationale et des réglementations locales de chaque université étant entendu que :</p>	<p>Preamble:</p> <p>The present Protocol of cotutela, redacted in the framework of the European Universities Initiative, aims to promote collaboration and mobility at the doctoral level between the member universities of the UNiTA-Universitas Montium Alliance. The institutions involved in the Protocol have the common goal of encouraging and developing scientific cooperation in the training of researchers and promoting the mobility of doctoral students from their respective institutions.</p> <p>By entering into this Protocol, each university commits to admitting the doctoral candidate to doctoral training at its respective institution, to provide joint supervision and to fulfil their obligations towards the doctoral candidate during the period of co-tutela.</p> <p>Each partner institution also commits to awarding a full doctoral degree to the doctoral candidate upon fulfilment of the requirements.</p> <p>The Parties agree to establish this protocol of international co-supervision of a thesis within the UNiTA Alliance, which specifies the terms of the collaboration. It is concluded in mutual understanding and respect of each university's national legislation and local regulations, on the understanding that :</p>	<p>Préambule :</p> <p>Le présent Protocole de cotutelle, redacté dans le cadre de l'initiative des Universités Européennes, vise à promouvoir la collaboration et la mobilité au niveau du doctorat entre les membres de l'Alliance UNiTA-Universitas Montium. Les institutions impliquées dans le Protocole ont pour but commun d'encourager et de développer la coopération scientifique dans la formation de chercheurs et de favoriser la mobilité des doctorants des universités respectives.</p> <p>En entrant dans ce Protocole, chaque université s'engage à admettre le candidat au doctorat à la formation doctorale dans son institution respective, à assurer une supervision conjointe et à remplir ses obligations envers le candidat au doctorat pendant la période de cotutelle.</p> <p>Chaque institution partenaire s'engage également à délivrer le diplôme de doctorat à part entière au candidat au doctorat s'il remplit les conditions requises par chaque établissement concerné.</p> <p>Les Parties conviennent de la mise en place de ce protocole de cotutelle internationale de thèse au sein de l'Alliance UNiTA, qui précise les termes de la collaboration. Le Protocole est conclu dans la compréhension et le respect mutuels de la législation nationale et des réglementations locales de chaque université étant entendu que :</p>
<p>Article 1.1: Purpose</p> <p>The Parties shall select the candidate according to the procedure in force at each institution, in compliance with the HRS4R approach.</p> <p>A specific bipartite doctoral co-supervision agreement will be established between the partner institutions. It will specify the information relating to the procedures for selecting the PhD candidate, his/her registration, personal data and diploma held, as well as the laboratories, thesis directors and financing of the thesis (origin, amount, duration and managing institution).</p>	<p>Article 1.1: Objet</p> <p>Les Parties sélectionneront le candidat selon la procédure en vigueur dans chaque établissement, dans le respect de la démarche HRS4R. Une convention bilatérale spécifique de cotutelle sera établie entre les établissements partenaires. Elle précisera les informations relatives aux modalités de sélection du candidat à la thèse, de son inscription, de ses données personnelles et diplôme détenu, ainsi que des laboratoires, directeurs de thèse et financement de la thèse (origine, montant, durée et établissement gestionnaire).</p>	<p>Artículo 1.1: Finalità</p> <p>Le Parti selezioneranno il candidato secondo la procedura in vigore presso ciascuna istituzione, nel rispetto dell'approccio HRS4R. Una convenzione di cotutela bilaterale specifica sarà stabilita tra le istituzioni partner. Essa preciserà le informazioni relative alle modalità di selezione del candidato, alla sua iscrizione, ai suoi dati personali e al diploma posseduto, così come ai laboratori, ai direttori di tesi e al finanziamento della tesi (origine, importo, durata e istituzione che lo gestisce).</p>	<p>Artigo 1.1: Objeto</p> <p>As Partes seleccionam o candidato de acordo com o procedimento vigente em cada estabelecimento, em conformidade com a abordagem HRS4R. Um acordo bilateral específico de co-supervisão será estabelecido entre os estabelecimentos parceiros. Nele serão especificadas as informações relativas ao procedimento de seleção do candidato, inscrição, dados pessoais e diploma obtido, bem como os laboratórios, diretores de tese e financiamento da tese (origem, valor, duração e instituição gestora).</p>
<p>Article 1.1: Object</p> <p>The Parties shall select the candidate according to the procedure in force at each institution, in compliance with the HRS4R approach.</p> <p>A specific bipartite doctoral co-supervision agreement will be established between the partner institutions. It will specify the information relating to the procedures for selecting the PhD candidate, his/her registration, personal data and diploma held, as well as the laboratories, thesis directors and financing of the thesis (origin, amount, duration and managing institution).</p>	<p>Article 1.1: Objeto</p> <p>Las Partes seleccionarán al candidato según el procedimiento vigente en cada institución, respetando el enfoque HRS4R.</p> <p>Se establecerá un acuerdo específico de cotutela doctoral bilateral entre las instituciones asociadas. En él se especificará la información relativa a los procedimientos de selección del doctorando, su inscripción, sus datos personales y su título, así como los laboratorios, los directores de tesis y la financiación de la tesis (origen, importe, duración e institución gestora).</p>	<p>Articolul 1.1: Obiect</p> <p>Partile vor selecta candidații la studii doctorale conform procedurii în vigoare în fiecare instituție, respectând abordarea HRS4R.</p> <p>Între instituțiile partener se va încheia un acord bilateral specific de cotutela. Acesta va stabili detaliile privind procedura de admitere la studiile universitare de doctorat, înmatricularea studentilor doctoranzi, datele cu caracter personal și datele personale de cercetare, conducătorii de doctorat și modul de finanțare a tezei (surșă, cantum, durată și instituția care administrează fondurile).</p>	<p>Artículo 1.1: Objeto</p> <p>Las partes seleccionarán al candidato según el procedimiento vigente en cada institución, respetando el enfoque HRS4R.</p> <p>Se establecerá un acuerdo específico de cotutela doctoral bilateral entre las instituciones asociadas. En él se especificará la información relativa a los procedimientos de selección del doctorando, su inscripción, sus datos personales y su título, así como los laboratorios, los directores de tesis y la financiación de la tesis (origen, importe, duración e institución gestora).</p>
<p>Article 1.1: Purpose</p> <p>The Parties shall select the candidate according to the procedure in force at each institution, in compliance with the HRS4R approach.</p> <p>A specific bipartite doctoral co-supervision agreement will be established between the partner institutions. It will specify the information relating to the procedures for selecting the PhD candidate, his/her registration, personal data and diploma held, as well as the laboratories, thesis directors and financing of the thesis (origin, amount, duration and managing institution).</p>	<p>Article 1.1: Objeto</p> <p>Las Partes seleccionarán al candidato según el procedimiento vigente en cada institución, respetando el enfoque HRS4R.</p> <p>Se establecerá un acuerdo específico de cotutela doctoral bilateral entre las instituciones asociadas. En él se especificará la información relativa a los procedimientos de selección del doctorando, su inscripción, sus datos personales y su título, así como los laboratorios, los directores de tesis y la financiación de la tesis (origen, importe, duración e institución gestora).</p>	<p>Articolul 1.1: Obiect</p> <p>Partile vor selecta candidații la studii doctorale conform procedurii în vigoare în fiecare instituție, respectând abordarea HRS4R.</p> <p>Între instituțiile partener se va încheia un acord bilateral specific de cotutela. Acesta va stabili detaliile privind procedura de admitere la studiile universitare de doctorat, înmatricularea studentilor doctoranzi, datele cu caracter personal și datele personale de cercetare, conducătorii de doctorat și modul de finanțare a tezei (surșă, cantum, durată și instituția care administrează fondurile).</p>	<p>Artículo 1.1: Objeto</p> <p>Las partes seleccionarán al candidato según el procedimiento vigente en cada institución, respetando el enfoque HRS4R.</p> <p>Se establecerá un acuerdo específico de cotutela doctoral bilateral entre las instituciones asociadas. En él se especificará la información relativa a los procedimientos de selección del doctorando, su inscripción, sus datos personales y su título, así como los laboratorios, los directores de tesis y la financiación de la tesis (origen, importe, duración e institución gestora).</p>

TITUL I. ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURES	TITUL I. PROCEDURES ADMINISTRATIVES	TITOLO I. PROCEDURE AMMINISTRATIVE	TITULO I. PROCEDIMIENTOS ADMINISTRATIVOS	TITULUL I. PROCEDURI ADMINISTRATIVE	TITULO I. PROCEDIMIENTOS ADMINISTRATIVOS
Article 2. Administrative procedures.	Article 2. Modalités administratives.	Articolo 2. Procedure amministrative.	Artigo 2. Procedimientos administrativos.	Articolul 2. Proceduri administrative.	Artículo 2. Procedimientos administrativos
<p>2.1 - Degree held : The authorisation to enroll in a PhD programme must respect the rules in force in the participant institutions.</p>	<p>2.1 - Diplôme obtenu : L'autorisation de doctorat doit respecter les règles en vigueur dans les pays partenaires à la cotutelle.</p>	<p>2.1 - Diploma posseduto : L'autorizzazione all'iscrizione al dottorato deve rispettare i regolamenti in vigore nei paesi partner della cotutela.</p>	<p>2.1 - Grau obținut : A autorizație pentru înscrierea în doctorat trebuie să respecte regulile în vigoare în ambele instituții participante.</p>	<p>2.1 - Studii necesare pentru admitere: Condițiile de admitere la studiile universitare de doctorat trebuie să respecte regulamentele în vigoare în ambele instituții participante.</p>	<p>2.1 - Título obtenido: La autorización para inscribirse en un programa de doctorado debe respetar las normas vigentes en las instituciones participantes.</p>
<p>2.2 - Thesis Duration : It is agreed by the Parties that the cotutelle agreement is valid until the candidate's career as PhD student is concluded. The doctoral program can be extended by amendment signed by the Parties. However, if the regulations in one of the partner countries of the bilateral specific agreement differ on this point, the rules of the institution managing the funding will prevail and a figure be specified in the bilateral specific agreement.</p>	<p>2.2 - Durée de la thèse : Il est convenu entre les Parties que la durée de la convention de cotutelle est valable jusqu'à la fin réglementaire du parcours doctoral. Le programme doctoral peut être prolongé par avenant signé des Parties. Toutefois, si la réglementation dans un des pays partenaires de la convention bilatérale spécifique diffère sur ce point, ce sont les règles de l'établissement gestionnaire du financement qui prévalent, comme cela sera spécifié dans la convention bilatérale spécifique.</p>	<p>2.2 - Durata della tesi : Le Parti convergono che la durata della convenzione di cotutela è valida sino al termine regolamentare del percorso dottorale. Il programma di dottorato può essere esteso mediante addendum sottoscritto dalle Parti. Tuttavia, se la normativa in uno dei Paesi partner firmatari della convenzione bilaterale specifica differisce su questo punto, prevarranno le norme dell'istituzione che gestisce il finanziamento e questo sarà specificato nella convenzione bilaterale specifica.</p>	<p>2.2 - Duración de la tese : Fica acordado entre as Partes que a duração do acordo de supervisão conjunta é válida até o final regulamentar do curso de doutoramento. O programa de doutoramento poderá ser prorrogado por acordo assinado pelas Partes. No entanto, se a regulamentação de um dos países parceiros do acordo bilateral específico diferir neste ponto, prevalecerão as regras da instituição gestora do financiamento, conforme especificado no acordo bilateral específico.</p>	<p>2.2 - Durata studiilor doctorale: Partile convin că acordul de cotutela este valabil până la finalizarea de către studentii doctoranzi a programului de studii doctorale. Acesta poate fi prelungit prin intermediul unui amendament semnat de partii. Totuși, în cazul în care regulamentele unei dintre țările de origine ale universităților semnatare ale acordului bilateral specific diferă în această privință, vor prevala regulile instituției care gestionează finanțarea, conform acordului bilateral specific.</p>	<p>2.2 - Duración de la tesis: Las Partes acuerdan que el acuerdo de cotutela es válido hasta la conclusión del doctorado por parte del candidato. La duración del doctorado puede ser prorrogada mediante una adenda firmada por las Partes. Sin embargo, si la normativa de uno de los países socios del convenio bilateral específico difiere en este punto, prevalecerán las normas de la institución que gestiona la financiación, y se especificará en el convenio específico bilateral.</p>
<p>2.3 - Residency and research periods : The doctoral research program will be carried out at the two universities involved in the co-supervised doctoral thesis. Each PhD student is required to spend at least 9 months outside his/her home university, preferably in the universities of the consortium. However, he/she must spend at least 6 months in the co-supervising university.</p>	<p>2.3 Périodes de résidence et de recherche : Le programme de recherche doctorale sera réalisé dans les deux universités concernées par la thèse de doctorat en cotutelle. Chaque doctorant est tenu de passer au moins 9 mois hors de son université d'origine, préférentiellement au sein des universités du consortium. Cependant, il/elle devra rester au moins 6 mois dans l'université de cotutelle.</p>	<p>2.3 - Soggetti e periodi di ricerca Il programma di ricerca dottorale sarà realizzato nelle due università interessate dalla tesi di dottorato in cotutela. Ciascun dottorando è tenuto a trascorrere almeno 9 mesi al di fuori della propria università di origine, preferibilmente presso università facenti parti del Consorzio. In ogni caso, ella/egli dovrà restare almeno 6 mesi presso l'università di cotutela.</p>	<p>2.3 - Periodos de residencia e de investigación : O programa de investigação de doutoramento será realizado nas duas universidades abrangidas pelo acordo de supervisão conjunta da tese de doutoramento. Cada estudante de doutoramento deve passar pelo menos 9 meses fora da sua universidade de origem, de preferência dentro das universidades do consórcio. No entanto, deve permanecer pelo menos 6 meses na 2ª universidade de co-supervisão.</p>	<p>2.3 Perioade de mobilitare și cercetare: Programul de cercetare doctorală se va desfășura în ambele universități implicate în coordonarea tezei de doctorat în cotutela. Fiecare student doctorand trebuie să petreacă cel puțin 9 luni în afara universității de proveniență, de preferință în universitățile consorțiului. Cu toate acestea, el/ea trebuie să petreacă cel puțin 6 luni în universitatea de cotutela.</p>	<p>2.3 - Periodos de residencia e investigación: El programa de investigación del doctorado se llevará a cabo en las dos universidades implicadas en la supervisión de la tesis doctoral en cotutela. Cada doctorando deberá pasar al menos 9 meses fuera de su universidad de origen, preferentemente en las universidades del consorcio. Sin embargo, deberá pasar al menos 6 meses en la Universidad de cotutela.</p>
<p>2.4 - Registration : The PhD student will be subject to a bilateral specific agreement and registered at both universities each year. The bilateral specific agreement will specify the mobility periods and the terms of payment of registration fees.</p>	<p>2.4 - Inscriptions : Le doctorant sera soumis à une convention bilatérale spécifique et inscrit auprès des deux universités de cotutelle chaque année. La convention bilatérale spécifique précisera les périodes de mobilité et les conditions de paiement des droits d'inscription.</p>	<p>2.4 - Registrazione : Il dottorando sarà soggetto ad una convenzione bilaterale specifica e iscritto ogni anno presso La convenzione bilaterale specifica preciserà i periodi di mobilità e i termini di pagamento delle tasse di registrazione.</p>	<p>2.4 - Inscripções : O doutorando estará sujeito a um acordo bilateral específico e inscrito anualmente nas duas universidades. O acordo bilateral específico especificará os períodos de mobilidade e as condições de pagamento das taxas de inscrição.</p>	<p>2.4 - Inscrieri: Studentii doctoranzi se vor supune prevederilor unui acord bilateral specific și se vor înscrie la ambele universități semnatare în fiecare an. Acordul bilateral specific va stabili perioadele de mobilitare și condițiile de plată a taxelor de înscriere.</p>	<p>2.4 - Registro: El estudiante de doctorado estará sujeto a un acuerdo bilateral específico y se inscribirá en ambas universidades cada año. El acuerdo bilateral específico especificará los períodos de movilidad y las condiciones de pago de las tasas de inscripción.</p>
<p>For each academic year the PhD student is required to re-enroll and his/her research activity must be positively assessed, in compliance with the regulations in force at each partner university.</p>	<p>Cheque année, le doctorant doit se réinscrire en thèse et son activité de recherche doit être évaluée positivement, conformément à la réglementation en vigueur dans chaque université partenaire.</p>	<p>Per ciascun anno accademico al dottorando è richiesto di reinscrivere e la sua attività di ricerca deve essere valutata positivamente in conformità con la normativa in vigore presso ciascuna delle università partner.</p>	<p>O doutorando deve proceder à sua inscrição em algum m. lectivo, devendo a sua atividade de investigação ser avaliada positivamente, de acordo com as normas vigentes em cada universidade parceira.</p>	<p>În fiecare an universitățile studentii doctoranzi trebuie să se reînmatriculeze, iar activitatea de cercetare a acestora trebuie să fie evaluată pozitiv, în conformitate cu regulamentele în vigoare în fiecare universitate parteneră.</p>	<p>En cada curso académico, el doctorando debe volver a matricularse y su actividad investigadora debe ser evaluada positivamente, en cumplimiento de la normativa vigente en cada universidad participante.</p>

<p>2.5 – Social welfare and civil liability coverage: Prior to his/her enrollment for each academic year: - The PhD student must be registered with the national social welfare coverage system of the country/countries in which they intend to stay, or possess equivalent social welfare insurance coverage for the duration of their stay; the social welfare coverage provided by the maintenance of the student's rights in their country of origin during the stay shall be considered a valid equivalent; - The PhD student must also possess valid civil liability coverage for the duration of his/her stay at the co-supervising universities.</p>	<p>2.5 – Couverture sociale et civile : Avant chaque inscription à l'année universitaire considérée: - Le doctorant devra être bénéficiaire de la couverture sociale d'un des pays au sein duquel/desquels il a vocation à séjourner ou d'une couverture sociale équivalente, et ce, pendant toute la durée de son séjour; doit notamment être considérée comme équivalente la couverture sociale résultant du maintien des droits de son pays d'origine durant le séjour; - Le doctorant devra également être titulaire d'une garantie responsabilité civile valable pour la durée, son séjour au sein des universités de co-étude.</p>	<p>2.5 – Copertura social e per responsabilità civile: Prima di iscriversi a ciascun anno accademico: - Il dottorando deve essere beneficiario della copertura sociale del/del Paese/i in cui intende soggiornare o di una copertura sociale equivalente per la durata del soggiorno; la copertura sociale fornita dal mantenimento dei diritti dello studente nel proprio Paese durante il soggiorno sarà considerata equivalente; - Il dottorando deve essere inoltre in possesso di una copertura per responsabilità civile valida per l'intero periodo del soggiorno presso le università di co-supervisione.</p>	<p>2.5 – Cobertura de segurança social e responsabilidade civil: Antes de cada inscrição para o ano letivo em causa: - O doutorando deve ser beneficiário de um sistema de segurança social do(s) país(es) em que pretende permanecer ou possuir cobertura social equivalente, válido pelo período da sua estadia; a cobertura de segurança social do país de origem deve ser considerada igualmente válida; - O doutorando deve também ser titular de uma cobertura de responsabilidade civil válida durante o período da sua estadia nas universidades de supervisão conjunta.</p>	<p>2.5 Asistența socială și asigurarea de răspundere civilă: Anterior înscrierii în fiecare an universitar: - studentul doctoranz trebuie să fie înscris în sistemul național de asistență socială din țara/țările în care intenționează să locuiască, sau să dețină o asigurare de asistență socială echivalentă pe durata șederii lor în respectiva țară; menținerea unei asigurări de asistență socială în țara de origine, pe durata șederii în străinătate, este considerată un echivalent valabil; - studentii doctoranzi trebuie, de asemenea, să dețină o asigurare de răspundere civilă valabilă pe durata șederii lor în universitățile de co-studiu.</p>	<p>2.5 – Cobertura de asistencia social y responsabilidad civil: Antes de su inscripción en cada curso académico: - el estudiante de doctorado deberá estar inscrito en el sistema nacional de cobertura social del país/países en los que pretenda realizar la estancia o poseer una cobertura de seguridad social equivalente para la duración de la misma; se considerará equivalentemente válida la cobertura de seguridad social proporcionada por el mantenimiento, durante la estancia, de los derechos del estudiante en su país de origen; - el estudiante de doctorado también debe poseer una cobertura de responsabilidad civil válida para la duración de su estancia en las universidades de co-estudio.</p>
<p>2.6 – Support for the PhD Student: During his/her stay, the Parties will facilitate the PhD Student's access to various local services, including in particular support services for international students, the various possibilities for arranging accommodations, and potential financial assistance.</p>	<p>2.6 – Soutien au doctorant : Pendant son séjour, les Parties favoriseront l'accès du doctorant aux différents services locaux, tels que notamment les services de soutien aux étudiants étrangers, les différentes possibilités d'hébergements et les aides financières potentielles.</p>	<p>2.6 – Supporto al dottorando : Durante il suo soggiorno, le Parti faciliteranno l'accesso del dottorando ai vari servizi di supporto, compresi, in particolare, i servizi di supporto agli studenti internazionali, le diverse possibilità di sistemazione abitativa e potenziale supporto finanziario.</p>	<p>2.6 – Apoio ao doutorando : No decorrer da sua estadia, as Partes garantirão que o doutorando tem acesso aos serviços de apoio a estudantes estrangeiros, opções de alojamento e eventuais ajudas financeiras.</p>	<p>2.6 – Sprijin pentru studenții doctoranzi: Pe durata șederii studenților doctoranzi în instituția gazdă, părțile le vor facilita accesul la diverse servicii locale, în special servicii de asistență pentru studenții internaționali, diferite posibilități de cazare, și eventual sprijin financiar.</p>	<p>2.6 – Apoyo al estudiante de doctorado: Durante su estancia, las Partes facilitarán el acceso del estudiante de doctorado a los diversos servicios locales, incluyendo, en particular, los servicios de apoyo a los estudiantes internacionales, las diversas posibilidades de alojamiento y las potenciales ayudas financieras.</p>
<p>Article 3 – Financial Arrangements No financial exchange is agreed between the Parties in the framework of this protocol. Each Party will bear the costs related to the implementation of the related missions and in particular all costs related to its personnel, missions, thesis direction, experimentation costs, thesis defence...</p>	<p>Article 3 – Modalités financières Aucun échange financier n'est convenu entre les Parties dans le cadre de ce protocole. Chaque Partie prendra en charge les frais liés à la mise en œuvre des missions afférentes et notamment tous frais relatifs à ses personnels, missions, direction de thèse, frais d'expérimentation, soutenance de thèse...</p>	<p>Article 3 – Disposizioni finanziarie Nessuno scambio finanziario viene convenuto tra le Parti nell'ambito del presente Protocollo. Ciascuna Parte prenderà in carico i costi legati alla realizzazione delle relative missioni e, in particolare, tutti i costi legati al proprio personale, alle missioni, alla direzione di tesi, alla sperimentazione, alla discussione della tesi....</p>	<p>Artigo 3 – Modalidades financeiras Nenhuma troca financeira é acordada entre as Partes no âmbito deste protocolo. Cada Parte suportará as despesas relacionadas com a implementação das missões relacionadas, nomeadamente todos os encargos relativos aos seus colaboradores, missões, orientação de tese, despesas de experimentação, defesas de tese....</p>	<p>Articolul 3 – Aranjamente financiare: Niciun fel de schimb financiar nu este convenit între părți în cadrul prezentului protocol. Fiecare parte va suporta costurile aferente implementării misiunilor care îi revin, în special toate costurile legate de personalul propriu, misiunile sale, conducerea tezei de doctorat, costuri pentru experimente, susținerea tezei....</p>	<p>Artículo 3 – Disposiciones financieras No se acuerda ningún intercambio financiero entre las Partes en el marco de este protocolo. Cada parte correrá con los gastos relacionados con la realización de las misiones correspondientes y, en particular, con todos los gastos relacionados con su personal, las misiones, la dirección de la tesis, los gastos de experimentación, la defensa de la tesis....</p>
<p>TITLE II. TRAINING AND RESEARCH CONDITIONS</p> <p>Article 4 : Pedagogical Approaches</p> <p>4.1 – PhD Directors : The PhD directors, one at each Partner University, and if applicable the co-directors, undertake to carry out their supervisory functions equitably. Only the two PhD directors, will be required to sign the bilateral specific agreement for a co-supervised doctoral research thesis.</p>	<p>TITRE II. LES CONDITIONS DE FORMATION ET DE RECHERCHE</p> <p>Article 4 : Modalités pédagogiques</p> <p>4.1 – Directeurs de thèse : Les directeurs, un dans chaque Université partenaire, et le cas échéant les co-directeurs de thèse, s'engagent à exercer leurs fonctions d'encadrement en toute équité. Seuls les directeurs de thèse seront tenus de viser la convention bilatérale spécifique pour une co-étude de thèse.</p>	<p>TITOLO II. CONDIZIONI PER LA FORMAZIONE E LA RICERCA</p> <p>Articolo 4: Approcci Pedagogici</p> <p>4.1 – Direttori di tesi : I Direttori di tesi, uno presso ciascuna Università Partner e, laddove previsti, i co-direttori, si impegnano ad esercitare le loro funzioni di supervisione in maniera equa. Solo ai due Direttori di tesi verrà richiesto di sottoscrivere la convenzione bilaterale specifica per una co-attività di tesi.</p>	<p>TÍTULO II. CONDIÇÕES DE FORMAÇÃO E DE INVESTIGAÇÃO</p> <p>Artigo 4: Modalidades pedagógicas</p> <p>4.1 – Orientadores de tese : Os orientadores, Sopor cada Universidade parceira, e, se for o caso, os co-orientadores de tese, comprometem-se a desempenhar as suas funções de supervisão com equidade. Apenas os orientadores de tese serão obrigados a assinar o acordo bilateral específico para supervisão conjunta de tese.</p>	<p>TITUL II. CONDIȚII DE PREGĂTIRE ȘI CERCETARE</p> <p>Articolul 4 : Abordări pedagogice</p> <p>4.1 – Conducători de doctorat: Conducătorii de doctorat, câte unul pentru fiecare universitate parteneră, și, după caz, membrii comisiilor de îndrumare, se angajează să își îndeplinească responsabilizabil de coordonare în mod echitabil. Acordul bilateral specific pentru coordonarea tezei de doctorat în co-studiu va fi semnat doar de cei doi conducători de doctorat.</p>	<p>TÍTULO II. CONDICIONES DE FORMACIÓN E INVESTIGACIÓN</p> <p>Artículo 4: Enfoques pedagógicos</p> <p>4.1 – Directores de doctorado: Los directores de doctorado, uno en cada universidad de co-estudio, y en su caso los co-directores, se comprometen a ejercer sus funciones de supervisión de forma equitativa. Solo los dos directores de doctorado, deberán firmar el acuerdo bilateral específico para una tesis de investigación doctoral codirigida.</p>

<p>In case of a change of PhD director(s), the Parties agree to provide notice promptly.</p>	<p>In cas de changement de directeur(s) de thèse, les Parties s'engagent à s'en informer dans les meilleurs délais.</p>	<p>In caso di modifica del/i direttore/i di tesi, le Parti si impegnano a darne celermente informazione.</p>	<p>Em caso de mudança do(s) orientador(es) de tese, as Partes comprometem-se a informar a contraparte com a maior brevidade possível.</p>	<p>În cazul schimbării conducătorului de doctorat, părțile convin să notifice cu promptitudine intervenții acestuia.</p>	<p>En caso de cambio de director(es) de tesis, las Partes se comprometen a notificarlo con prontitud.</p>
<p>4.2 – Obligations of the PhD Student : The PhD Student is required to comply with the legal and regulatory rules in force in the countries of each co-supervising university, as well as with the requirements set forth by the Doctoral Schools to which they are attached. The modalities are defined in the bilateral specific agreement signed by the PhD student.</p>	<p>4.2 – Obligations du doctorant : Le doctorant est tenu de satisfaire aux règles législatives et réglementaires en vigueur au sein des pays de chaque université de co-tutelle ainsi qu'aux exigences définies par l'École doctorale de rattachement. Les modalités sont définies dans la convention bilatérale spécifique signée par le doctorant.</p>	<p>4.2 – Obblighi del dottorando : Il dottorando è tenuto al rispetto delle leggi e dei regolamenti in vigore nei Paesi di ciascuna università di co-tutela, così come dei requisiti definiti dalla Scuola di Dottorato di riferimento. Le modalità sono definite nella convenzione bilaterale specifica sottoscritta dal dottorando.</p>	<p>4.2 – Obrigações do doutorando : O doutorando é obrigado a cumprir as normas legislativas e regulamentares em vigor nos países de cada universidade de supervisão conjunta, bem como os requisitos definidos pela escola de doutoramento a que está vinculado. Os termos são definidos no acordo bilateral específico assinado pelo doutorando.</p>	<p>4.2 – Obligațiile studentilor doctoranzi: Studentii doctoranzi trebuie să respecte normele legale și reglementare în vigoare în țările de origine ale facultății dintr-o universitate implicată în cotutela, precum și procedurile și metodologiile stabilite de școlile doctorale de care aparțin. Modalitățile specifice sunt definite în acordul bilateral semnat de fiecare student doctorand.</p>	<p>4.2 - Obligaciones del doctorando: El doctorando está obligado a cumplir con las normas legales y regulatorias vigentes en los países de cada universidad de co-tutela, así como con los requisitos establecidos por las Escuelas de Doctorado a las que están adscritos. Las modalidades se definen en el acuerdo bilateral específico firmado por el doctorando.</p>
<p>Article 5: Hosting – Liability – Insurance In the context of this Protocol, personnel of one other Party may be hosted. During their stay on the hosting Party's premises, hosted personnel shall be subject to the internal regulations, and must respect the health and safety regulations applied by the hosting Party. They must comply with the instructions provided for the use of the equipment and facilities, such as in particular the operating instructions, operating hours, potential risks, and specific protections. Notwithstanding the foregoing, the hosted personnel shall remain under the authority of their employer, which shall continue to fulfil all its corresponding obligations in its capacity as employer, such as in particular its obligations related to remuneration, social welfare obligations, taxation, obligations regarding workplace accidents, occupational diseases, its administrative management prerogatives, and civil liability for the actions of all hosted personnel under its authority. The Parties declare that they are fully in compliance with their obligations in regard to social security contributions, VAT and other taxes, and have subscribed statutory insurance to cover workplace accidents as well as civil liability insurance. Certificates from the competent entities are available upon request by the hosting Party.</p>	<p>Article 5: Accueil-Responsabilités- Assurances Dans le cadre de ce Protocole, des personnels d'une autre Partie pourront être accueillis. Pendant leur séjour dans les locaux de la Partie accueillante, le personnel accueilli sera soumis au règlement intérieur et devra respecter les règles d'hygiène et de sécurité de la Partie accueillante. Il devra suivre les indications données concernant l'utilisation des équipements et les installations, telles que notamment les instructions opératoires, horaires, risques encourus et protections spécifiques. Nonobstant ce qui précède, Le personnel accueilli reste placé sous l'autorité de son employeur, qui continue d'assumer envers lui l'ensemble des obligations afférentes à sa qualité d'employeur, telles que notamment ses obligations de rémunérations, ses obligations sociales, fiscales, ses obligations relatives à la couverture en matière d'accidents du travail, de maladies professionnelles, ses prérogatives administratives de gestion, ainsi que la responsabilité civile concernant les actes du personnel accueilli restant sous son autorité. Les Parties déclarent satisfaire à leurs obligations en matière de sécurité sociale, de TVA et d'impôts et avoir contracté une assurance légale contre les accidents du travail ainsi qu'une assurance responsabilité civile. A la demande de la Partie accueillante, une attestation des instances compétentes peut être fournie.</p>	<p>Articolo 5: Accoglienza – Responsabilità – Assicurazione Nel contesto del presente Protocollo, il personale dell'altra Parte può essere ospitato. Durante il soggiorno nei locali della Parte ospitante, il personale ospitato sarà soggetto ai regolamenti interni e dovrà rispettare la normativa sulla salute e sulla sicurezza della Parte ospitante. Esso dovrà conformarsi alle istruzioni fornite per l'utilizzo della strumentazione e dei locali, in particolare, le istruzioni d'uso, gli orari di apertura, i rischi potenziali e le protezioni specifiche. Nonostante quanto sopra, il personale ospitato rimarrà sotto l'autorità del datore di lavoro, che continuerà ad adempiere a tutti i propri obblighi connessi: alla remunerazione, alla copertura sociale, alla malattia professionale, alle sue prerogative di gestione amministrativa e alla responsabilità civile per le azioni di tutte le persone ospitate sotto la sua autorità. Le Parti dichiarano di essere pienamente a norma in relazione ai loro obblighi in materia di contribuzione per la sicurezza sociale, IVA ed altre tasse, e di aver sottoscritto assicurazione legale a copertura degli incidenti sul lavoro nonché per responsabilità civile. Su richiesta della Parte ospitante, può essere fornita attestazione rilasciata dal competente ufficio.</p>	<p>Artigo 5: Acolhimento-Responsabilidades- Seguros No âmbito do presente Protocolo, poderá ser recebido pessoal de outra Parte. Durante a sua estadia nas instalações da Parte anfitriã, o pessoal acolhido estará sujeito ao regulamento interno e deverá cumprir as regras de saúde e segurança da Parte anfitriã. Deve seguir as indicações dadas relativamente à utilização dos equipamentos e instalações, nomeadamente as instruções de funcionamento, horários, incidentos e proteções específicas. Sem prejuízo do que precede, o pessoal acolhido permanecerá sob a autoridade do seu empregador, que continua a assumir para com ele todos as obrigações relativas à sua contratação de empregador, tais como as suas obrigações remuneratórias, as suas obrigações sociais, as obrigações fiscais, as suas obrigações relativas à cobertura de acidentes de trabalho, doenças profissionais, suas prerrogativas de gestão administrativa, bem como a responsabilidade civil pelos atos dos funcionários recebidos que permanecem sob a sua autoridade. As Partes declaram que cumprem as suas obrigações em matéria de segurança social, IVA e impostos e que subscreveram um seguro legal contra os acidentes de trabalho, bem como um seguro de responsabilidade civil. A pedido da Parte anfitriã, pode ser fornecido um certificado das autoridades competentes.</p>	<p>Articolul 5: Găzduire – Răspundere – Asigurare În virtutea prezentului protocol, personalul unei alte părți poate beneficia de găzduire la una dintre celelalte instituții participante. Pe durata șederii în sediul instituției gazdă, beneficiarul mobilității va fi ținut să respecte regulamentul intern și normele de sănătate și securitate la locul de muncă aplicabile instituției gazdă. Acesta trebuie să respecte instrucțiunile privind folosirea echipamentelor și instalațiilor, în special instrucțiunile de utilizare a acestora, programul de funcționare, potențialele riscuri și măsurile de protecție specifice. Fără a aduce atingere dispozițiilor anterioare, personalul aflat în stație în instituția gazdă rămâne sub autoritatea angajatorului său, care va continua să își îndeplinească toate obligațiile care îl revin în calitate de angajator, în special cele privind remunerarea, asistența socială, impozitărea, asigurarea împotriva accidentelor de muncă, bolile profesionale, prerogativele manageriale, precum și răspunderea civilă pentru acțiunile întreprinse personalul găzduit temporar de instituția parteneră aflat sub autoritatea sa. Partea declară că își îndeplinește corresponsabilitățile referitoare la contribuțiile de asigurări sociale, TVA și alte impozite, precum și că nu contractează altă asigurare legală pentru acoperirea accidentelor de muncă, cât și o asigurare de răspundere civilă. Un certificat în acest sens poate fi eliberat de autoritățile competente.</p>	<p>Artículo 5: Alojamiento – Responsabilidad – Seguro En el marco del presente Protocolo, personal de una de las Partes podrá ser acogido. Durante su estancia en los locales de la Parte anfitriona el personal acogido estará sujeto al reglamento interno y deberá respetar las normas de seguridad e higiene aplicadas por la Parte anfitriona. Deberá respetar las instrucciones de uso de los equipos e instalaciones, en particular las instrucciones de uso, los horarios de funcionamiento, los riesgos potenciales y las protecciones específicas. Sin perjuicio de lo anterior, el personal acogido permanecerá bajo la autoridad de su empleador, que continuará cumpliendo con todas sus obligaciones correspondientes en su calidad de empleador, tales como, sus obligaciones relativas a la remuneración, sus obligaciones de previsión social, la fiscalidad, las obligaciones relativas a los accidentes de trabajo, las enfermedades profesionales, sus prerrogativas de gestión administrativa y la responsabilidad civil por los actos de todo el personal acogido bajo su autoridad. Las Partes declaran estar al corriente de sus obligaciones en materia de cotizaciones a la seguridad social, IVA y otros impuestos, y haber suscrito un seguro obligatorio que cubre los accidentes laborales, así como un seguro de responsabilidad civil. Los certificados de las entidades competentes están disponibles a petición de la Parte anfitriona.</p>
<p>Each Party will take personal responsibility, insofar as each is concerned, for damages of any kind, including physical injury, material damages, or immaterial damages, that</p>	<p>Cheque Partie fera son affaire, chacune en ce qui la concerne, des dommages de toute sorte, tels que notamment les dommages corporels, matériels ou immatériels, causés</p>	<p>Ciascuna Parte si assumerà la personale responsabilità, per quanto di propria competenza, per danni di qualunque tipo, comprese ferite fisiche, danni materiali o</p>	<p>Cada Parte será responsável, no que lhe diz respeito, por danos de qualquer natureza, nomeadamente lesões corpóreas, danos materiais ou imateriais, causados pelos seus</p>	<p>Fiecare parte își asumă răspunderea personală, în măsura în care o privește, pentru daunele de orice fel, inclusiv</p>	<p>Cada una de las Partes asumirá la responsabilidad personal, en lo que a cada una concierne, por los daños de cualquier tipo, incluidos los daños físicos, materiales o</p>

<p>may be caused to third parties. In the context of this Protocol by any action of their own, and/or of their assets, and/or of their personnel, as well as for all related legal claims and proceedings.</p> <p>Each Party will take personal responsibility, insofar as each is concerned, for damages of any kind that may be caused or arise on the occasion of the execution of this Protocol to itself, to the personnel it employs, and/or to the assets and equipment belonging to it, except where the same results from the negligence or fault of the other Party and/or its personnel.</p> <p>Each Party agrees to maintain, or to subscribe if required, the necessary insurance coverage to guarantee itself against all risks for which it may remain liable under this Protocol.</p>	<p>parteurs actes et/ou leurs biens et/ou leurs personnes, aux tiers dans le cadre de ce Protocole et de toutes réclamations et actions en justice afférentes.</p> <p>Chaque des Parties fera son affaire, chacune en ce qui la concerne, des dommages ou pertes de toute sorte qui pourraient survenir ou être causés, à l'occasion de l'exécution du Protocole, à elle-même, aux personnes qu'elle emploie et/ou aux biens et matériels lui appartenant, sauf s'ils résultent de la faute ou de la négligence de l'autre Partie et/ou de son personnel.</p> <p>Chaque des Parties s'engage à maintenir ou, à souscrire si besoin est, les assurances nécessaires pour se garantir contre tous les risques restant à sa charge au titre du Protocole.</p>	<p>Immateriali, che possono essere causate a terzi, nel presente Protocollo e a causa di beni, persone o attività proprie, o di loro risorse e/o del loro personale così come di tutte le pretese e i procedimenti giudiziari connessi.</p> <p>Ciascuna Parte si assuma la personale responsabilità, per quanto di propria competenza, per i danni di qualunque tipo che possono essere causati o scaturire in occasione dell'esecuzione del presente Protocollo arrecati a sé, al personale impiegato, e/o alle risorse ed attrezzature che gli appartengono, eccetto dove gli stessi risultino da negligenza o colpa dell'altra Parte e/o del suo personale.</p> <p>Ciascuna Parte si impegna a mantenere, o, addove necessario, a sottoscrivere la copertura assicurativa necessaria a garantirsi contro tutti i rischi a suo carico nell'ambito del presente Protocollo.</p>	<p>atos e/ou bens e/ou pessoais, a terceiros, no contexto deste Protocolo e todas as ações e procedimentos legais relacionados.</p> <p>Cada uma das Partes será responsável, no que lhe diz respeito, por danos ou perdas de qualquer tipo que possam surgir ou ser causados, durante a execução do Protocolo, a si mesma, ao pessoal que emprega e materiais que lhe pertencem, salvo se resultarem de culpa ou negligência da outra Parte e/ou do seu pessoal.</p> <p>Cada uma das Partes compromete-se a manter ou, se necessário, a subscrever os seguros necessários para garantir a cobertura de todos os riscos de que é responsável ao abrigo do Protocolo.</p>	<p>vătămări corporale, prejudicii materiale sau imaterialie care pot fi cauzate terților în contextul prezentului protocol prin orice acțiune proprie, și/sau a lucrurilor care le aparțin, și/sau a personalului lor, precum și pentru toate cererile în justiție și procedurile legale aferente.</p> <p>Fiecare parte își asumă răspunderea personală în măsură în care o privește, pentru daunele de orice natură care pot surveni sau pot fi cauzate, cu excepția eventualelor prejudicii personale și materiale proprii propriu, sau bunurilor și echipamentelor aceluia, cu excepția cazului în care respectivele daune sunt rezultatul neglijenței ori culpei celuilalt părți și/sau a personalului său.</p> <p>Fiecare parte este de acord să mențină, sau să contracteze, după caz, asigurările necesare pentru a-și acoperi toate riscurile pentru care i s-ar putea atrage răspunderea în temeiul prezentului protocol.</p>	<p>Immaterialies, que puedan ser causados a terceros en el contexto del presente Protocolo por cualquier acción propia, y/o de sus bienes, y/o de su personal, así como por todas las reclamaciones y procedimientos legales relacionados.</p> <p>Cada una de las Partes asumirá la responsabilidad personal en lo que a cada una se refiere, por los daños de cualquier tipo que puedan causarse o surgir con motivo de la ejecución del presente Protocolo a sí misma, al personal que emplea y/o a los bienes y equipos que le pertenecen, excepto cuando los mismos sean resultado de la negligencia o la culpa de la otra Parte y/o de su personal.</p> <p>Cada Parte se compromete a mantener, o a suscribir si es necesario, la cobertura de seguro necesaria para asegurarse contra todos los riesgos por los que pueda seguir siendo responsable en virtud del presente Protocolo.</p>
<p>Article 6 – Confidentiality and Intellectual Property</p> <p>The provision of Articles 11 (Confidentiality and data protection), 12 (Processing personal data) and 13 (Ownership and other rights on the Results) of the Consortium Agreement to which the Parties are signatories and referenced UPPA CONT-2021-0091 shall apply.</p>	<p>Article 6 – Confidentialité et Propriété Intellectuelle</p> <p>Il est fait application des dispositions des Articles 11 (Confidentialité et protection des données), 12 (Traitement de données personnelles) et 13 (Propriété et autres droits sur les Résultats) de l'Accord de Consortium dont les Parties sont signataires et référencé UPPA CONT-2021-0091.</p>	<p>Articolo 6 – Confidentialità e Proprietà Intellettuale</p> <p>Si applicano le disposizioni di cui agli articoli 11 (Confidenzialità e Protezione dei Dati), 12 (Elaborazione di dati personali) e 13 (Proprietà e altri diritti sui risultati) dell'Accordo di Consorzio registrato come UPPA CONT-2021-0091, di cui le Parti sono firmatarie.</p>	<p>Artigo 6: Confidencialidade e Propriedade Intelectual</p> <p>Aplicam-se as disposições do artigo 11 (Confidencialidade e proteção de dados), 12 (Processamento de dados pessoais) e 13 (Propriedade e outros direitos sobre os Resultados) do Acordo de Consórcio cujas Partes são signatárias e referenciado na UPA sob o n.º 1211151.</p>	<p>Articolul 6 – Confidențialitate și Proprietate Intelectuală</p> <p>Prezentului protocol îi sunt aplicabile prevederile articolului 11 (Confidențialitate și protecția datelor), 12 (Prelucrarea datelor cu caracter personal) și 13 (Dreptul de proprietate și alte drepturi asupra rezultatelor cercetării) din Acordul de parteneriat în care părțile sunt semnatar, și identificat cu numărul de referință UPPA CONF-2021-0091.</p>	<p>Artículo 6 - Confidencialidad y propiedad Intelectual</p> <p>Se aplicará lo dispuesto en los artículos 11 (Confidencialidad y protección de datos), 12 (Tratamiento de datos personales) y 13 (Propiedad y otros derechos sobre los Resultados) del Acuerdo de Consorcio del que las Partes son signatarias y referenciado UPPA CONT-2021-0091.</p>
<p>6.1 – Publication on Open Access</p> <p>In compliance with European rules, the Parties are encouraged to disseminate in Open Access the scientific outputs of the projects, either by publishing in an Open Access journal or by depositing the authorized open version in an open access repository, subject to the confidentiality provisions (Article 11 de Consortium Agreement).</p>	<p>6.1 – Publication en libre accès</p> <p>Conformément aux règles européennes, les Parties sont encouragées à diffuser en Open Access les résultats scientifiques des projets, soit en publiant dans une revue en Open Access, soit en déposant la version ouverte autorisée dans un dépôt en Open Access, sous réserve des dispositions de confidentialité (Article 11 de l'accord de Consortium).</p>	<p>6.1 – Pubblicazione su Open Access</p> <p>In conformità con la legislazione europea, le Parti sono incoraggiate a disseminare su Open Access i risultati scientifici dei progetti, sia mediante pubblicazione su rivista "Open Access" sia depositando la versione "open" autorizzata in un repository Open Access, soggetta alle clausole di confidenzialità (Articolo 11 dell'Accordo di Consorzio).</p>	<p>6.1 – Publicação em acesso livre</p> <p>De acordo com as regras Europeias, as Partes são encorajadas a divulgar em Acesso Aberto os resultados científicos dos projetos, quer publicando numa revista de Acesso Livre, quer depositando a versão livre autorizada num repositório de Acesso Aberto, sujeito a disposições de confidencialidade. (Artigo 11 do Contrato de Consórcio).</p>	<p>6.1 – Publicarea în regim Open Access</p> <p>În conformitate cu normele europene, părțile sunt încurajate să difuzeze în regim Open Access rezultatele științifice ale proiectelor de cercetare, fie prin publicarea lor într-o revistă cu acces liber, fie prin arhivarea versiunii în acces liber autorizate într-o arhivă cu acces liber, sub rezerva respectării prevederilor privind confidențialitatea (articolul 11 din Acordul de parteneriat).</p>	<p>6.1 – Publicación en acceso abierto</p> <p>En cumplimiento de la normativa europea, se anima a las Partes a difundir en acceso abierto los resultados científicos de los proyectos, ya sea publicando en una revista de acceso abierto o depositando la versión abierta autorizada en un repositorio de acceso abierto, sin perjuicio de las disposiciones de confidencialidad (artículo 11 del Acuerdo de Consorcio).</p>
<p>TITRE III : DEFENCE, DIPLOMAS AND TITLE OF DOCTOR</p> <p>Article 7 : Thesis defence</p> <p>7.1 – Thesis defence jury and thesis defence location :</p> <p>The rapporteurs and juries will be appointed in accordance with the laws and regulations in effect in the countries of the Parties hereto.</p>	<p>TITRE III. SOUTÈNANCE, DIPLOMES ET TITRE DE DOCTEUR</p> <p>Article 7 : La soutenance</p> <p>7.1 – Jury de soutenance et lieu de soutenance</p> <p>Les rapporteurs et les jurys seront désignés conformément aux lois et réglementations en vigueur dans les pays des Parties au présent Protocole.</p>	<p>TITOLO III : DISCUSSIONE, DIPLOMA E TITOLO DI DOCTORE</p> <p>Articolo 7: Discussione della tesi</p> <p>7.1 – Commissione e sede per la discussione della tesi :</p> <p>I valutatori e i commissari saranno nominati in conformità con le leggi e i regolamenti in vigore nei Paesi delle Parti.</p>	<p>TITULU III. DEFENSA, DIPLOMAS E GRAU DE DOCTOR</p> <p>Artigo 7. A defesa</p> <p>7.1 – Juri e lugar de defesa</p> <p>Os jurts serão nomeados de acordo com as leis e regulamentos em vigor nos países das Partes deste Protocolo.</p>	<p>TITULU III. SUSTINEREA TEZEI, DIPLOMELE SI TITULU DE DOCTOR</p> <p>Articolul 7 : Sustinerea publică a tezei de doctorat</p> <p>7.1 – Comisia de susținere publică a tezei de doctorat și locul susținerii tezei</p> <p>Referenții și comisia de doctorat vor fi numiți în conformitate cu legis și regulamentele în vigoare în țările părților.</p>	<p>TITULO III: DEFENSA, DIPLOMAS Y TITULO DE DOCTOR</p> <p>Artículo 7 : Defensa de la tesis</p> <p>7.1 – Tribunal de defensa de la tesis y lugar de defensa de la tesis:</p> <p>Los relatores y los jurados serán designados de acuerdo con las leyes y reglamentos vigentes en los países de las Partes.</p>

<p>The place of thesis defence will be determined at the time of jury appointment. The viva voce thesis defence will take place only once, in accordance with the regulations in effect in the countries of the Parties. The defence may also be made by means of videoconference systems if admitted by both universities.</p> <p>The organization of the defence will be the responsibility of the university where the defence will take place. As to the costs for accommodation and transportation they will be defined case by case in the specific bilateral agreement, in accordance with the regulations in force.</p>	<p>Le lieu de soutenance sera déterminé lors de la désignation du jury. La thèse donnera lieu à une soutenance unique, en accord avec les règles en vigueur dans les pays des Parties. La soutenance pourra aussi se faire en visioconférence, si cela est admis par les deux universités.</p> <p>Les modalités de l'organisation de la soutenance, de même que la prise en charge des frais d'hébergement et de transport y afférents seront pris en charge dans l'université où aura lieu la soutenance, en accord avec la réglementation en vigueur et la convention bilatérale spécifique établie.</p>	<p>La sede per la discussione della tesi sarà definita al momento della nomina della Commissione. La discussione avverrà una sola volta, in conformità con i regolamenti in vigore nei Paesi delle Parti. La discussione può avvenire anche attraverso sistemi di videoconferenza, se ammessi da entrambe le Università.</p> <p>L'organizzazione della discussione sarà responsabilità dell'università presso cui si svolgerà la discussione.</p> <p>Per quanto attiene ai costi di soggiorno e di trasporto, questi saranno definiti caso per caso nell'accordo bilaterale specifico, in conformità con i vigenti regolamenti.</p>	<p>O lugar da defesa será determinado quando o júri for nomeado. A tese dará origem a uma única defesa, de acordo com as regras em vigor nos países das Partes. A defesa também pode ser feita por videoconferência, se isso for permitido pelos dois universidades.</p> <p>Os termos da organização da defesa, bem como o pagamento das respectivas despesas de alojamento e transporte serão definidos na universidade onde a defesa decorrerá, de acordo com a regulamentação em vigor e o acordo bilaterale específico estabelecido.</p>	<p>O lugar de defensa de la tesis se determinará en el momento de la designación del Jurado. La defensa de la tesis tendrá lugar una sola vez, de acuerdo con la normativa vigente en los países de las Partes. La defensa también podrá realizarse mediante sistemas de videoconferencia si lo admiten ambas universidades.</p> <p>La organización de la defensa será responsabilidad de la universidad en la que se realice la defensa. En cuanto a los costes de alojamiento y transporte se definirán caso por caso en el acuerdo bilaterale específico de acuerdo con la normativa vigente.</p>	<p>7.2 - Languages: The thesis must be written in English or/and in one of the languages of the partner universities. A substantial abstract as well as the introduction and conclusion will be written in English or/and in one of the languages of the Alliance universities, but in this case, the language used must be different from that of the thesis. The thesis defence will be orally presented in one of the languages spoken in the countries of the Alliance or in English.</p>	<p>7.2 - Langues: La thèse sera rédigée en anglais et/ou dans une des langues des universités partenaires. Un résumé substantiel ainsi que l'introduction et la conclusion seront rédigés en anglais et/ou dans une langue des pays des universités de l'Alliance mais, dans ce dernier cas, la langue utilisée devra être différente de celle de la thèse. La soutenance de la thèse se fera dans une des langues parlées dans les pays de l'Alliance ou en anglais.</p>	<p>7.2 - Lingua: La tesi deve essere scritta in inglese o/e in una delle lingue delle Università partner. Un riassunto sostanziale, così come l'introduzione e la conclusione saranno scritte in inglese o/e in una delle lingue delle Università parte dell'Alleanza; in tal caso, la lingua utilizzata deve essere diversa da quella della tesi. La discussione avverrà in forma orale in una delle lingue parlate nei Paesi dell'Alleanza o in inglese.</p>	<p>7.2 - Línguas: A tese será escrita em inglês e/ou num dos idiomas das universidades parceiras. Um resumo alargado, bem como a introdução e a conclusão, serão redigidos em inglês e/ou numa língua dos países das universidades da Aliança, mas, neste último caso, a língua utilizada deve ser diferente da utilizada na tese. A defesa da tese será numa das línguas oficiais dos países da Aliança ou em inglês.</p>	<p>7.2 - Limbile de redactare și susține a tezei de doctorat: Teza de doctorat trebuie să fie redactată în limba engleză sau/și într-una dintre limbile universității partener. Un rezumat substanțial, precum și introducerea și concluziile vor fi redactate în limba engleză sau/și într-una dintre limbile universității Aliației, dar în acest caz, limba utilizată trebuie să fie diferită de cea în care este redactată teza. Susținerea publică a tezei va fi realizată oral, într-una dintre limbile vorbite în țările Aliației sau în limba engleză.</p>	<p>7.2 - Idiomas: La tesis debe estar escrita en inglés y/o en una de las lenguas de las universidades asociadas. Un resumen sustancial, así como la introducción y las conclusiones, se redactarán en inglés o/y en una de las lenguas de las universidades de la Alianza, pero en este caso, la lengua utilizada debe ser diferente a la de la tesis. La defensa de la tesis se llevará a cabo en una de las lenguas habladas en los países de la Alianza o en inglés.</p>	<p>7.3 - Storage, description and reproduction of the thesis: The storage, description and reproduction of the thesis will be carried out in compliance with the rules in force in each co-supervising university. At the time thesis is submitted to one of the two universities, the doctoral student will have to notify the other university.</p>	<p>7.3 - Dépot, signalement et reproduction de la thèse: Le dépôt, le signalement et la reproduction de la thèse sont effectués conformément à la législation et réglementation en vigueur dans chacune des universités de cotutelle. Au moment où la thèse est déposée dans une des deux universités, le doctorant devra aviser l'autre université.</p>	<p>7.3 - Deposito, descrizione e riproduzione della tesi: Il deposito, la descrizione e la riproduzione della tesi avverranno in conformità con i regolamenti vigenti in ciascuna delle università di supervisione. Nel momento in cui la tesi viene consegnata ad una delle due università, il dottorando dovrà darne comunicazione all'altra.</p>	<p>7.3 - Depósito, descripción e reproducción da tese: O arquivamento, apresentação e reprodução da tese são realizados de acordo com a legislação e regulamentação em vigor em cada uma das universidades de supervisão conjunta. Quando a tese for submetida a uma das universidades, o doutorando deverá notificar a outra universidade.</p>	<p>7.3 - Ahvireta, descrierea și reproducerea tezei: Activarea, descrierea și reproducerea tezei se vor efectua cu respectarea normelor în vigoare în fiecare universitate implicată în cotutela. La momentul depunerii tezei la una dintre cele două universități, doctorantul trebuie să înștiințeze cealaltă universitate despre acest lucru.</p>	<p>7.3 - Almacenamiento, descripción y reproducción de la tesis: El almacenamiento, la descripción y la reproducción de la tesis se llevarán a cabo de acuerdo con las normas vigentes en cada universidad de cotutela. En el momento de presentar la tesis en una de las dos universidades, el doctorando deberá notificar a la otra universidad.</p>	<p>Article 8 - The Degree and Title of Doctor: In accordance with the laws and regulations in effect in the countries of each co-supervising university, upon recommendation by the jury, and upon consideration of the thesis defence packet, the Parties undertake to simultaneously and separately award their national doctorate degree with the mention of the cotutelle with the Partner University, as established in this Protocol.</p>	<p>Article 8 : Le Diplôme et le titre de Docteur En conformité avec les législations et règlements en vigueur au sein des pays de chaque université de cotutelle, sur proposition conforme du jury et au vu du dossier de soutenance, les Parties s'engagent à reconnaître pleinement la validité du diplôme délivré, comme établi dans ce Protocole.</p>	<p>Artículo 8 - Diploma e título de Doctor: En conformidad con las leyes y reglamentos vigentes en los países de cada universidad de supervisión, su propuesta de la Comisión e in consideración del dossier de discusión, las Partes se comprometen a reconocer simultáneamente y por separado su título de doctor nacional con la mención de la cotutela con la Universidad asociada, tal como se establece</p>	<p>Artigo 8. O Diploma e o grau de Doutor De acordo com as leis e regulamentos vigentes nos países de cada universidade de supervisão conjunta, sob proposta do júri e após a defesa, as Partes comprometem-se a atribuir, simultaneamente e individualmente, o grau de doutor nacional, com menção à supervisão conjunta, conforme estabelecido neste Protocolo.</p>	<p>Articolul 8: Diploma și titlul de Doctor: Conform legilor și reglementărilor în vigoare în țările din care provin universitățile implicare în cotutela, la recomandarea consiliilor de doctorat și cu luarea în considerare a dosarului de susținere a tezei, Partea se angajează să recunoască pe deplin validitatea diplomei de doctor unic, elaborată cu mențiunea cotutellei cu</p>	<p>Artículo 8 - El grado y el título de doctor: De acuerdo con las leyes y reglamentos vigentes en los países de cada universidad de cotutela, previa propuesta conforme del tribunal tras la violación del dossier de defensa de la tesis, las Partes se comprometen a otorgar simultáneamente y por separado su título de doctor nacional con la mención de la cotutela con la Universidad asociada, tal como se establece</p>
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<p>In application of the European Qualifications Framework (EQF), the PhD is classified in the National Qualifications Framework, which allows the title of Doctor to be awarded.</p> <p>The diplomas will acknowledge that the PhD has been obtained within the UNITA-Universitas Montium Alliance.</p>	<p>De la même façon, en application du cadre européen des certifications (CEC), le Doctorat est classé au cadre national de certification qui permet de délivrer le titre de Docteur.</p> <p>Les diplômes délivrés feront apparaître que le doctorat a été obtenu dans le cadre de l'Alliance UNITA-Universitas Montium.</p>	<p>In application del Quadro Europeo delle Qualifiche (EQF), il Doctorato viene classificato nel Quadro Nazionale delle Qualifiche, che consente il rilascio del titolo di Dottore.</p> <p>I diplomi espliciteranno che il Doctorato è stato ottenuto nel quadro dell'Alleanza UNITA-Universitas Montium.</p>	<p>Em aplicacão do Quadro Europeu de Qualificações (QE/Q), o Doutoramento é classificado no quadro nacional de certificação que permite a emissão do título de Doutor.</p> <p>Os diplomas atribuídos mencionarão que o Doutoramento foi obtido no âmbito da Aliança UNITA-Universitas Montium.</p>	<p>universitatea parteneră, astfel cum este stabilit în prezentul protocol.</p> <p>În aplicarea Cadrelui european al calificărilor (CEC), doctoratul este clasificat în Cadru Național al Calificărilor, care permite acordarea titlului de Doctor.</p> <p>Diplomele eliberate studenților doctoranzi vor atesta faptul că titlul de doctor a fost obținut în cadrul Alianței UNITA-Universitas Montium.</p>	<p>en el presente Protocolo.</p> <p>En aplicación del Marco Europeo de Cualificaciones (MEC), el doctorado está clasificado en el Marco Nacional de Cualificaciones que permite otorgar el título de Doctor.</p> <p>Los diplomas reconocerán que el doctorado se ha obtenido dentro de la Alianza UNITA-Universitas Montium.</p>
<p>Article 9 : Duración – Termination</p> <p>9.1 – Duraton : This Protocol will take effect from the date of last signature for a period of five (5) Years and ignore rule all the specific agreements negotiated during its course of validity within the UNITA Alliance. At the end of this period, the Protocol may be extended by amendment, signed by the authorized representatives of the Parties, which specifies the purpose of this extension. All provisions of this Protocol which are intended to apply after its termination or cancellation shall remain in force.</p>	<p>Article 9 : Durée – Résiliation</p> <p>9.1 – Durée : Le présent Protocole prend effet à compter de la date de dernière signature pour une durée de cinq (5) ans, et il régit tous les accords de courtes spécificités négociés durant la période de validité du Protocole UNITA. A la fin de cette période, le Protocole pourra être prolongé par avenant, signé par les représentants dûment habilités des Parties, qui précise l'objet de cette prolongation. Toutes dispositions du présent Protocole ayant vocation à s'appliquer après sa terminaison ou sa résiliation, demeureront en vigueur.</p>	<p>Artículo 9 : Durata – Cesación</p> <p>9.1 – Durata El presente Protocolo prende efecto dalla data di ultima sottoscrizione per un periodo di cinque (5) anni e disciplinera tutti gli accordi specifici negoziati durante il suo corso di validità nell'ambito dell'Alleanza UNITA. Al termine di questo periodo, il Protocollo potrà essere esteso per mezzo di addendum, sottoscritto dai Rappresentanti legali delle Parti, che preciserà la finalità di tale estensione. Rimangono in vigore tutte le disposizioni del presente Protocollo intese a trovare applicazione dopo il suo termine o la sua cancellazione.</p>	<p>Artigo 9 : Duracao – Resolucao</p> <p>9.1 – Duracao : Este Protocolo entra em vigor a partir da data da ultima assinatura por um periodo de 5 (cinco) anos, e regerá todos os acordos específicos de supervisão conjunta negociados durante o periodo de vigência do Proloco UNITA. Fimdo esse prazo, o Protocolo poderá ser prorrogado por meio de adenda, assinada pelos representantes devidamente autorizados das Partes, que especifique o objetivo dessa prorrogação. Todos os dispositivos deste Protocolo destinados a serem aplicados após a sua resolução ou rescisão permanecerão em vigor.</p>	<p>Articolul 9 : Durata protocolului – Rezilierea protocolului :</p> <p>9.1 – Durata protocolului : Prezentul protocol intră în vigoare de la data ultimei semnături pentru o perioadă de cinci (5) ani, și va guverna toate acordurile specifice negociate pe parcursul perioadei sale de valabilitate în cadrul Alianței UNITA. La sfârșitul acestei perioade, Protocolul poate fi prelungit printr-un amendament, semnat de reprezentanții autorizați ai părților, care să precizeze scopul acestui prelungiri, care să precizeze aplicarea Protocolului care va avea de a se aplica ulterior rezilierii sau anulării acestuia vor rămâne în vigoare.</p>	<p>Artículo 9: Duración - Terminación</p> <p>9.1. Duración: El presente Protocolo entrará en vigor a partir de la fecha de su última firma por un periodo de cinco (5) años y regirá todos los acuerdos específicos negociados durante su vigencia en el seno de la Alianza UNITA. Al final de este periodo, el Protocolo podrá ser prorrogado mediante una adenda, firmada por los representantes autorizados de las Partes, que especifique el objeto de esta prórroga.</p> <p>Todas las disposiciones del presente Protocolo que estén destinadas a aplicarse después de su terminación o anulación seguirán en vigor.</p>
<p>9.2 – Termination : if one of the Parties fails to fulfil one of the Protocol's obligations, the other Parties may decide to terminate the Protocol to the defaulting Party's detriment if, within thirty (30) days of sending a registered letter with recorded delivery, the defaulting Party has still not complied with its obligations. The exercise of this right of termination shall not release the Parties, in particular the defaulting Party, from the continued fulfilment of its obligations until the effective date of termination.</p>	<p>9.2 – Résiliation : Dans l'hypothèse où une des Parties viendrait à manquer à une des obligations du Protocole, les autres Parties pourront prononcer la résiliation du Protocole aux torts de la Partie défaillante si, dans les trente (30) jours de envoi d'une lettre recommandée avec demande d'avis de réception, la Partie défaillante ne s'est toujours pas conformée à ses obligations. L'exercice de cette faculté de résiliation ne dispense pas la Partie défaillante de remplir ses obligations contractées jusqu'à la date d'effet de la résiliation et ce, sous réserve des dommages éventuellement subis par les autres Parties du fait de la résiliation de l'accord.</p>	<p>9.2 Cessazione Nel caso in cui una delle Parti venga meno a uno degli obblighi previsti dal Protocollo, le altre Parti possono decidere di porre termine al Protocollo a danno della Parte inadempiente se, entro trenta (30) giorni dall'invio di una lettera raccomandata con avviso di ricevuta, la Parte inadempiente non si sia conformata agli obblighi.</p> <p>L'esercizio del diritto di cessazione non dispensa la Parti, ed in particolare la Parte inadempiente, di adempiere agli obblighi contrattuali fino alla data di effetto della cessazione.</p>	<p>9.2 – Resolucao : Na eventualidade de uma das Partes não cumprir uma das obrigações do Protocolo, as outras Partes podem determinar a rescisão do Protocolo às custas da Parte incumpridora se, no prazo de 30 (trinta) dias contados do envio de carta registrada com aviso de recepção, a Parte incumpridora ainda não tiver cumprido suas obrigações. O exercício deste direito de rescisão não isenta as Partes, nomeadamente a Parte incumpridora de cumprir as obrigações contratuais até a data efetiva da rescisão.</p>	<p>9.2 – Rezilierea protocolului : În cazul în care una dintre părți nu își îndeplinește oțre care din obligatiile ce îi revin în virtutaa protocolului, celelalte părți pot decide rezilierea protocolului în detrimentul părții care nu și-a executat obligatiia, dacă în termen de treizeci (30) de zile de la trimiterea către aceasta a unei scrisori recomandate cu aziz de primire, respectiva parte nu și îndeplinește obligatiile. Exercițiu acestuia drept de reziliere nu va dispensa părțile, în special partea culpabilă, de obligația conformării față de prevederile protocolului până la data efectivă a rezilierii acestuia.</p>	<p>9.2 - Terminación: En caso de que una de las Partes incumpla una de las obligaciones del Protocolo, las demás Partes podrán decidir rescindir el Protocolo en perjuicio de la Parte incumplidora si, en el plazo de treinta (30) días a partir del envío de una carta certificada con acuse de recibo, la Parte incumplidora sigue sin cumplir sus obligaciones. El ejercicio de este derecho de rescisión no eximirá a las Partes, en particular a la Parte incumplidora, del cumplimiento continuado de sus obligaciones hasta la fecha efectiva de rescisión.</p>
<p>Article 10: Processing of Personal Data</p> <p>The Parties must process the personal data covered by this Protocol in compliance with the applicable European legislation on data protection (General Data Protection Regulation) and/or any national laws derived thereof.</p>	<p>Article 10 : Traitement des données personnelles</p> <p>Les Parties doivent traiter les données personnelles visées par le présent Protocole conformément à la législation européenne applicable en matière de protection des données (Règlement général sur la protection des données) et/ou à toute loi nationale qui en découle.</p>	<p>Articolul 10: Elaborazione di dati personali</p> <p>Le Parti sono tenute a elaborare i dati personali coperti dal presente Protocollo in conformità con la legislazione Europea applicabile in materia (Regolamento Generale sulla Protezione dei Dati) e/o di ogni legge nazionale che da essa derivi.</p>	<p>Artigo 10 : Tratamento dos dados pessoais</p> <p>As Partes devem processar os dados pessoais abrangidos por este Protocolo de acordo com a legislação Europeia de proteção de dados aplicável (Regulamento Geral de Proteção de Dados) e/ou qualquer lei nacional dela derivada.</p>	<p>Articolul 10: Prelucrarea datelor cu caracter personal</p> <p>Părțile sunt ținute să prelucreză datele cu caracter personal reglementate de prezentul protocol în conformitate cu legislația europeană aplicabilă protecției datelor (Regulamentul general privind protecția datelor) și/sau cu orice legislație națională derivată din aceasta.</p>	<p>Artículo 10. Tratamiento de datos personales</p> <p>Las Partes deben tratar los datos personales contemplados en el presente Protocolo de conformidad con la legislación europea aplicable en materia de protección de datos (Reglamento General de Protección de Datos) y/o las leyes nacionales derivadas.</p>

<p>Article 11 : Langue – Applicable Law – Dispute Resolution This Protocol is written in the five languages of the Alliance and in English. In case of dispute, the Parties shall endeavour to reach an amicable settlement. If the disagreement persists, the dispute will be submitted to the competent courts with jurisdiction at the defendant's domicile. The English version of this Protocol will prevail (as the text was drafted and negotiated in English) This Protocol is hereby made in six (6) original copies, of which each Party keeps one (1).</p>	<p>Art 11: Langage – Loi applicable – Litiges Ce Protocole est rédigé dans les cinq langues de l'Alliance et en anglais. En cas de différend, les Parties s'efforceront de le régler à l'amiable. En cas de désaccord persistant, le différend sera soumis au tribunal compétent du domicile du défendeur. La version anglaise du Protocole sera alors la version de référence (comme tenu de sa préparation commune en langue anglaise). Le présent Protocole est établi en six (6) exemplaires originaux, un (1) pour chaque Partie.</p>	<p>Articolo 11 : Lingua – Normativa applicabile Risoluzione delle controversie Il Presente Protocollo è redatto nelle cinque lingue dell'Alleanza e in inglese. In caso di controversia, le Parti tenteranno di raggiungere un accordo per vie amichevoli. Nel caso in cui il disaccordo persista, la controversia sarà sottoposta al tribunale competente del rispondente. La versione inglese del presente Protocollo prevarrà (poiché il testo è stato redatto e negoziato in inglese). Il presente Protocollo è redatto in sei (6) copie originali, di cui ciascuna Parte terrà una (1).</p>	<p>Artigo 11: Língua – Lei aplicável – Litígios Este Protocolo está redigido nas cinco línguas da Aliança e em inglês. Em caso de litígio, as Partes desenvolverão todos os esforços para resolvê-lo de forma amigável. Em caso de persistência do desentendimento, o litígio será submetido ao tribunal competente do domicílio do requerido. A versão inglesa do Protocolo será então a versão de referência (dada a sua preparação comum em inglês). Este Protocolo é estabelecido em 6 (seis) cópias originais, uma (1) para cada Parte.</p>	<p>Articolul 11: Limba protocolului – Legea aplicabilă – Soluționarea litigiilor Prezentul protocol este redactat în cele cinci limbi ale Alianței și în limba engleză. În caz de litigiu, părțile se vor strădui să ajungă la o înțelegere pe cale amabilă a acestuia. Dacă litigul persistă, el va fi înaintat instanțelor competente de la domiciliul părților. Versiunea în limba engleză a acestui protocol va prevala (evănit în vedere că textul a fost redactat și negociat în limba engleză). Prezentul protocol est redactat în șase (6) exemplare originale, câte unul (1) pentru fiecare parte.</p>	<p>Artículo 11: Lengua – Ley aplicable – Resolución de litigios Este Protocolo está redactado en las cinco lenguas de la Alianza y en inglés. En caso de litigio, las Partes se esforzarán por llegar a un acuerdo amistoso. Si el desacuerdo persiste, el litigio se someterá a los tribunales competentes con jurisdicción en el domicilio del demandado. La versión inglesa del presente Protocolo prevalecerá (ya que el texto fue redactado y negociado en inglés) El presente Protocolo se redacta en seis (6) ejemplares originales, de los cuales cada Parte conserva uno (1).</p>
<p>Pour l'Université Savoie Mont Blanc Le Président de l'USMB Philippe GALLEZ</p> <p>En Timisoara, el 2 Junio 2022</p>					